

20 November 2025

**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE "FAMILY – HEALTH – DISEASE"
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS**

Edited by: Luba Ślósarz, Iwona Zborowska, Anna Dąbek, Andrzej Jarynowski, Mariola Seń

UNIwersYTET MEDYCZNY
IM. PIASTÓW ŚLĄSKICH WE WROCLAWIU

Univerzita Tomáše Bati ve Zlíně
Fakulta humanitních studií

Edited by: Luba Ślósarz, Iwona Zborowska, Anna Dąbek, Andrzej Jarynowski,
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The Impact of a Child's Cancer on the Family

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Introduction: A diagnosis of cancer represents a great psychological burden for a child and his or her loved ones. It has an impact not only on the sick child and his or her family, but also on his or her social environment. The aim of the research was to examine the impact of a child's cancer on the family environment and family resilience.

Methodology and research sample: We used the Family Hardiness Index questionnaire (McCubbin, Thompson & McCubbin, 1996) and the Family Environment Scale questionnaire to collect data. The research sample consisted of 79 parents - caregivers of a child with cancer.

Results: We recorded relatively high family resilience. There are weak to strong relationships between the family environment and resilience. Cohesion, expressiveness and conflict emerged as the three most important dimensions of the family environment in relation to family resilience. Cohesion in the concept of the family environment proved to be the main predictor of family resilience.

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Conclusion: The atmosphere in the family, mutual relationships, communication between members and the overall approach of parents to the child is extremely important for the child's further development, for his overall health, for his recovery.

Key words: family, family environment, family resilience, oncologically ill child

**„The Family System as a Risk Factor or a Source of Support in
Recovery?": The Dual Role of the Family in the Context of Eating
Disorders in Adolescents**

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Eating disorders are among the most common mental health problems in adolescents. When a minor suffers from an eating disorder, the illness affects the entire family system. The family can act as both a protective factor and a risk factor in the development of the disorder in the child.

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In Poland, anorexia nervosa occurs in approximately 0.1–5.7% of adolescents. However, research indicates that up to 13.3% of young people in Poland meet the diagnostic criteria for anorexia. Family environments characterised by conflict avoidance, overprotection, and poor problem-solving abilities are considered risk factors. Recent findings highlight parental perfectionism as a particularly important factor in both the onset and maintenance of eating disorders in children. In addition, parental mood and anxiety disorders, higher levels of parental control, and lower levels of care further contribute to this risk. Studies also emphasise the different roles of maternal and paternal characteristics. Maternal psychopathology, including anxiety and depressive symptoms, as well as concerns about the child's body weight, have been linked to disordered eating behaviours in offspring. In contrast, paternal psychological overcontrol is associated with a higher incidence of bulimia nervosa in children. The interdisciplinary model of eating disorder treatment addresses not only individual therapy for the child but also systemic changes within the family. Meta-analyses consistently identify family therapy as the leading treatment method for children and adolescents with anorexia nervosa. Moreover, recent evidence suggests that early family involvement can lead to lasting therapeutic outcomes.

The family environment thus represents both a risk factor and a potential source of therapeutic support. Identifying family characteristics that contribute to the development of eating disorders, and integrating this knowledge into healthcare practice, may enhance the effectiveness of prevention and intervention strategies.

Key words: eating disorders, adolescents, family system, risk factors, family therapy

**Nutritional Education in Chronic Kidney Disease: A Collaborative Support
both for Patient and Family**

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Chronic kidney disease (CKD) requires a comprehensive treatment approach, in which dietary management plays a key role in improving patient outcomes during the conservative care phase. Equally important is the education and involvement of the family [1]. Both patients and their families face challenges in adhering to prescribed renal diets. Family support is crucial in maintaining dietary behaviours [2] and malnutrition prevention [1]. Patients feeling high level of familiar support obtain impaired dietary behaviours.

As early as 2010, it was noted that educational programs supported by multidisciplinary health teams and self-help groups have shown to improve lifestyle and dietary habits significantly [3,4]. CKD in children affects the entire family [5]. Better diet quality is associated with a reduced likelihood of CKD progression [6]. Patterns like the Mediterranean, DASH [7] or plant-dominant low protein diet [8–11], which emphasize fruits, vegetables, and low protein intake, are as beneficial in reducing CKD progression as protein restriction itself in managing CKD [7].

Implementing educational strategies that involve both patients and their families can significantly improve dietary adherence and overall health outcomes. This includes providing

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clear, consistent nutritional information and fostering a supportive environment [12]. While elimination-based dietary strategies may offer therapeutic benefits, their improper implementation can lead to adverse outcomes, including kidney overload, malnutrition, micronutrient deficiencies, and electrolyte disturbances in individuals with CKD.

Key words: CKD, education, family, diet

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The Influence of Nutrition on the Course of Huntington’s Disease

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Introduction: Huntington's disease is a rare, progressive neurodegenerative disorder, the course of which is associated not only with motor and cognitive impairment but also with numerous nutritional challenges. Dysphagia, energy imbalance, and progressive weight loss lead to an increased risk of malnutrition, which significantly deteriorates patients' quality of life. Appropriate dietary intervention may constitute an important supportive element of therapy, alleviating disease consequences and improving daily functioning.

Aim of the presentation: The aim of this study was to discuss the impact of nutrition on the course of Huntington's disease, with particular focus on the main nutrition-related problems—dysphagia, impaired energy metabolism, and weight loss.

Methods: This work is a narrative review based on an analysis of scientific literature available in PubMed, Google Scholar, and both Polish and English-language printed sources. Articles published within the last several years were primarily considered, while older studies of high scientific relevance were included in cases of limited availability of newer data.

Conclusions:

- Proper nutrition plays a crucial role in the course of Huntington's disease, influencing both patients' overall health status and the progression rate of neurodegenerative symptoms.
- A well-balanced diet may contribute to improved quality of life and potentially slow the development of specific disease manifestations.

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- Patients with Huntington's disease face numerous nutrition-related problems, including dysphagia, increased caloric requirements, altered appetite, weight loss, and malnutrition. These issues threaten nutritional status and necessitate individualized dietary interventions.
- Energy imbalance in HD patients can result in gradual weight loss, often despite increased appetite and caloric intake.
- Compared with control groups, HD patients present significantly lower BMI and other anthropometric parameters regardless of age or sex. Moreover, a positive correlation has been observed between the severity of motor symptoms and the reduction of fat mass and muscle mass.

Key words: Huntington's disease, nutrition, diet therapy, dysphagia

**Ability to actively collaborate with healthcare providers as part of health
literacy**

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Objectives: The aim of the research was to determine the ability to actively collaborate with healthcare providers as one of the domains of health literacy in patients with arterial hypertension. The research was carried out within the framework of the KEGA project No. 010KU-4/2022 Implementation of elements of support for health literacy of the adult population into education in the field of nursing.

Material and methodology: The research group consisted of 391 respondents with arterial hypertension. The respondents were aged from 20 to 88 years, the average age of the respondents was 53.41 years. The research group included 207 (52.94%) women and 184 (47.06%) men. Data collection was carried out using the Slovak version of the standardized measurement tool Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ) based on the HLQ™ license agreement.

Results: The ability to actively collaborate with healthcare providers is the sixth of the nine domains of the HLQ measurement tool and is examined by five items. We recorded an average score of 3.4 out of a maximum possible value of 5 for respondents. We further verified the influence of the respondents' age, gender, education and place of residence on the ability to actively collaborate with healthcare providers. Using the ANOVA test, age was confirmed as a significant factor in the ability to actively collaborate with healthcare providers.

This ability decreases with age. Gender does not affect the area of domain 6, which we found using the t-test. An ANOVA test was used at the 0.05 level to verify the influence of education. Based on the F and Fcrit values, we recommend accepting the conclusion that education has been confirmed as a significant factor in active collaboration with healthcare providers. Respondents with higher education also have a higher ability to collaborate with healthcare providers. Residence was confirmed as a statistically significant factor in active cooperation

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with healthcare providers using a t-test of two means. Respondents living in cities have a higher ability to cooperate than people living in rural areas.

Conclusion: The ability to actively cooperate with healthcare providers as one of the domains of health literacy in patients with arterial hypertension represents an important area in the context of both prevention and therapy. A low level of domain 6 in the HLQ assessment tool means that people are passive in accessing the healthcare system. They do not actively seek information, advice and healthcare services. They accept the information that is available and do not ask questions if something is unclear or they do not understand something. They do not try to provide everything necessary for their health.

Key words: Health Literacy Questionnaire (HLQ), Ability to actively collaborate with health care providers, Patient, Arterial hypertension, Health literacy.

**Barriers and Challenges in Home Nursing Care of Chronically Ill Adults
and Their Families**

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Introduction: Home nursing care has become an essential pillar of the healthcare system in the context of population ageing and the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases. The transfer of care to the home environment enhances patient comfort and system efficiency, yet it also brings new challenges. Nurses are at the centre of this care, working not only with the patient but also with the family. The level of family support significantly influences the course of care, the patient's quality of life, and the workload of nurses.

Material and Methods: The study was conducted among nurses employed in home nursing agencies using a non-standardized questionnaire of original design. The research focused on logistical, communication, professional, and systemic barriers, including experiences of cooperation with family members. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and the chi-square test ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Results: The findings confirmed that insufficient family education and their limited preparedness to provide basic care increase the workload of nurses. Some families represent an important partner for ensuring continuity of care, while others may pose challenges due to limited cooperation or differing attitudes towards recommendations. Additionally, nurses reported excessive patient numbers per shift, insufficient funding, and high administrative burden. A statistically significant relationship was demonstrated between nurses' level of education and job satisfaction.

Conclusions: Home nursing care for chronically ill adults is effective only when the family is actively involved in the process. A lack of family cooperation and education represents a significant barrier that may threaten continuity and quality of care. Recommended measures include systematic family education, strengthening interdisciplinary communication,

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optimizing patient-to-nurse ratios, and improving the legislative and financial framework of home nursing services.

Key words: home nursing care, family, nursing barriers, chronic diseases, nurse

Quality of life of children with cerebral palsy and their legal guardians

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Introduction: Cerebral palsy (CP) is the most common cause of physical disability in children, resulting from non-progressive disturbances in the developing brain. It affects motor and postural functions and often leads to long-term limitations in daily activities. Given the complexity of CP, it is essential to assess not only the child's condition but also the broader impact on family life.

Aim of study: The aim of this study was to evaluate the quality of life (QoL) of children with cerebral palsy in specific functional domains and to assess the impact of the disease on family functioning, particularly before and after botulinum toxin type A (BTX-A) treatment.

Materials and Methods: The study involved 42 participants- children with CP and their legal guardians. A diagnostic survey was conducted using the PedsQL 4.0 Generic Core Scales (age-

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specific), the PedsQL 2.0 Family Impact Module, and a questionnaire on sociodemographic and clinical data. Assessments were performed before and three weeks after BTX-A injections.

Results: Prior to treatment, caregivers rated the child's emotional functioning highest and physical functioning lowest. Post-treatment, school functioning showed the greatest improvement. Children also rated school functioning highest and physical functioning lowest both before and after injections, with improved scores post-treatment. Caregivers reported the lowest QoL in the domain of worry and the highest in family relationships and cognitive functioning. Strong correlations were observed between child and family QoL scores both before and after treatment.

Conclusions: Children with CP have reduced QoL, particularly in physical functioning. BTX-A treatment improves selected QoL domains but does not eliminate limitations. Family functioning significantly affects the child's QoL, underscoring the importance of a holistic, family-centered approach in the care of children with CP.

Key words: children, cerebral palsy, quality of life, family functioning, Botulinum toxin type A.

Destigmatization of mentally ill and their families - a call for nursing

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Introduction: For nursing, the implementation of destigmatization activities is a challenge related to reducing the consequences of mental illness on the patient and his family..

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Material and methods: To identify the level of awareness and opinions of nurses on the implementation of destigmatization, we conducted a survey in March 2024 using a self-constructed questionnaire. The survey sample consisted of 103 nurses in nursing practice. To evaluate the results of the survey, we used the absolute and nominal value of the respondents' answers.

Results: More than 60% of respondents to our survey rate their level of awareness about destigmatization activities as insufficient. More than 57% agree with the statement that increasing health literacy in the field of mental health is one of the important destigmatization activities. More than 52% of respondents agree with the statement that community care has destigmatization potential.

Conclusion: In order for nurses to actively participate in destigmatization activities, it is necessary to educate them in the given area and support them to actively participate in the implementation of strategies for destigmatization of mental illnesses, as part of nursing practice.

Key words: Nursing. Stigma. Destigmatization. Mental illness.

**„The Role of the Family in Nutritional Prehabilitation of Patients with Colorectal
Cancer – Enhancing Adherence Potential”**

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Nutritional prehabilitation is an important part of the comprehensive preparation of patients with colorectal cancer for surgical and oncological treatment. An adequate nutrition reduces the risk of complications, accelerates recovery and improves the overall prognosis. However, the effectiveness of nutritional interventions largely depends on patient adherence – their willingness and ability to implement recommendations.

In this process the family is invaluable. Family members are often responsible for meal planning, shopping, food preparation and providing everyday emotional support. Their involvement in nutritional education, as well as close cooperation with the clinical dietitian, significantly enhances the chances of successful implementation of dietary recommendations. For oncology patients, who frequently struggle with appetite loss, nausea, or aversion to food, family support can be crucial to maintaining an adequate energy and protein balance.

The presentation will discuss practical strategies for involving family members in the nutritional prehabilitation process and provide guidance for therapeutic teams on how to effectively strengthen adherence through the activation of the patient's immediate environment.

Key words: nutritional prehabilitation, colorectal cancer, perioperative care

Nutritional literacy of oncology patients in home care

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INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE "FAMILY – HEALTH – DISEASE"
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Edited by: Luba Ślórsarz, Iwona Zborowska, Anna Dąbek, Andrzej Jarynowski, Mariola Seń

Introduction: In patients with oncological disease are nutritional disorders a risk factor, which complicate anti-tumor treatment and significantly shorten the survival of patients. In practice, the key condition for success is the assessment of the nutritional status and early nutritional intervention. Nutritional literacy is extremely important for restoring health. It also includes understanding the information necessary to address malnutrition in the cancer patient.

Objective: The main objective of the paper is explain the procedures of nursing interventions in ensuring the nutrition of a malnourished patient.

Methods: The main method is a case study. The choice of the respondent was deliberate. These selection criteria were: a patient with an oncological diagnosis and malnutrition, willing to cooperate. We included a 68-year-old patient with esophageal cancer in the study. The patient provided us with information about his health condition voluntarily and agreed to its processing.

Results: Based on nutritional anamnesis, anthropometric measurements and laboratory tests, the patient's nutritional status was evaluated as malnutrition. Over the course of five months, we ensured that the patient's nutritional needs were met through a percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy through prescribed nutritional interventions - administration of diet No. 1 and nutridrinks. We managed to stabilize the patient's body weight during the monitored period.

Conclusion: Malnutrition is the most common accompanying diagnosis in oncology patients. Timely planning and implementation of nutritional intervention is important for patients who have a percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy.

Key words: Nutrition literacy. Onkologic patient. Nutritional interventions. Percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy. Home care.

Teamwork and patient safety in long-term care facilities

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Edited by: Luba Ślórsarz, Iwona Zborowska, Anna Dąbek, Andrzej Jarynowski, Mariola Seń

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Introduction: A teamwork collaboration has a significant importance for patient safety. Effective team collaboration therefore means providing good and safe patient care, and at the same time, it also influences the quality of the provided care. In Slovakia, there is a lack of research addressing this issue in the context of long-term care.

Objective: The aim of our study was to describe impact of teamwork on patient safety in long-term care facilities.

Material and methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from March to September 2023 using the Nursing Teamwork Survey (NTS) and the Nursing Home Survey on Patient Safety Culture (NHSPSC) tool. The research sample consisted of 585 healthcare professionals working in long-term care facilities in Slovakia.

Results: Highest-rated areas were team support ($m = 4.1$) and team leadership ($m = 4.1$). In contrast, team orientation received the lowest rating ($m = 2.9$), showing a tendency to avoid conflict resolution and a weaker level of feedback. The team leader plays a significant role, as their skills, availability, and fairness are reflected in the overall satisfaction of the staff. Correlational analysis confirmed a statistically significant relationship between patient safety, dimensions of patient safety, and the quality of care provided ($p \leq 0.05$).

Conclusions: The results of our research have allowed us to identify the extent of team-work in the long-term care. Management of these facilities should place an emphasis on regular training, fostering open communication, and creating systems that enable staff to effectively share information. The findings emphasize the need to implement specific measures to improve the quality of care provided.

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Key words: teamwork, safety, safety culture, NTS, NHSPSC, long-term care facilities

**Factors influencing the level of physical activity of elderly patients in
institutional treatment**

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Introduction: Physical activity and independence in activities of daily living are important areas that need to be supported even in the institutional treatment of seniors. Physical activity is not only important in terms of mobility of patients in old age, but it is also an element of prevention. A good level of functional fitness is a positive prognostic indicator in acute conditions in geriatrics, but it is also important in preventing complications of pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment. It is therefore essential to support factors that have a positive effect on activity and eliminate factors that have a negative effect.

Objective, Material and methods: The aim was to identify factors influencing the physical fitness of seniors in institutional health and social care. The research population consisted of 333 elderly patients. Of the above number, 102 respondents were from the Czech Republic and 231 from Slovakia. Their average age was 79.75. The research methods were Barthel test,

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Physical Fitness Test, Karnofsky index, Handgrip test, anthropometric measurements, document analysis, nutritional anamnesis.

Results: After analyzing practical and empirical methods, we identified factors that positively and negatively affect the physical fitness of seniors. Positive factors: interdisciplinary cooperation of team members, regular monitoring of the functional status of the elderly, individually adjusted interventions focused on nutritional support and physical activation. Negative factors: health status - 22.75% oncological diseases, risky pharmacotherapy - 20%, poor nutritional status - 34 respondents had an arm circumference of less than 21, 90 seniors had confirmed malnutrition. Negative factors also included low muscle strength - average values for men 16.3 and women 10.7, deterioration in activities of daily living - 64 respondents were highly dependent.

Conclusion: Research has confirmed that by early identification of risk factors and support of positive factors and regular monitoring of the functional status of patients in older age, we will achieve the elimination of destabilization of the health status of seniors in acute and long-term treatment.

Key words: Activation. Monitoring of functional status. Risk factors. Elderly patients. Physical activity.

**The impact of the education of nurses working in hospitals in the Slovak
Republic on their work motivation**

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Introduction: Nurses' education is one of the factors influencing their work motivation, as it is closely related to their social status, self-efficacy, and autonomy in the profession.

Objective: The aim was to identify the relationship between nurse education and the types of their work motivation.

Material and methods: The study has a cross-sectional descriptive correlation design. The sample consisted of 1023 nurses from 11 hospitals in the Slovak Republic. Data were collected from February to May 2025 using the Multidimensional Work Motivation Scale (MWMS). Statistical analyses included descriptive measures and generalized linear modeling with quasi-Gaussian assumptions. Cronbach's alpha for the subscales representing types of work motivation ranged from 0.80 (externalized material regulation) to 0.92 (identified regulation). Nurses responded to 19 statements using the 7-point Likert scale (1 'not at all' to 7 'exactly').

Results: The nurses achieved the highest level in identified regulation (M=5.1) and intrinsic motivation (M=5.0). University education of nurses significantly reduced external material regulation ($\beta -0.190$; $p=0.010$). However, university educated nurses living in a partner

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relationship had this type of motivation increased (β 0.194; $p=0.026$). Completion of specialization and/or certification training significantly increased externalized social regulation (β 0.667; $p<0.001$), material regulation (β 0.566; $p<0.001$), introjected regulation (β 0.326; $p = 0.003$) and amotivation (β 0.448; $p=0.002$). However, in nurses with specialization and/or certification training, their amotivation (β -0.017 ; $p<0.001$), externalized social (β -0.017 ; $p=0.001$), and material regulation (β -0.016 ; $p=0.001$) were reduced with increasing years of practice. Nurses with completion of specialization and/or certification training with increasing years of practice had higher intrinsic motivation (β 0.012; $p=0.015$).

Conclusions: The results point to the complexity of the impact of nursing education on nurses' work motivation. Supporting nurses in completing specialization and training can increase their intrinsic motivation, which is related to experiencing meaningfulness of work and satisfaction.

Supported by VEGA 1/0123/24: Work motivation of nurses and its impact on turnover: sequential explanatory mixed-method study

Key words: nursing education, work motivation, intrinsic motivation, specialization training

Dimitrios Paouris: Workplace Mobbing Among Nurses in Slovakia: The Impact of Education, Workplace Type, and Job Position.

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Introduction – Workplace bullying, a widespread phenomenon, significantly impacts interpersonal relationships, mental health, professional performance, and organizational efficiency in healthcare. Defined as repeated behaviors intended to intimidate or degrade, bullying thrives in hierarchical, high-stress environments like hospitals, where nurses face disproportionate risk. Such behaviors harm morale, increase turnover, and jeopardize patient safety through errors and negligence. Understanding its prevalence and contributors is essential for fostering healthier work environments and improving healthcare outcomes.

Methods – This cross-sectional descriptive study followed the STROBE guidelines. A Slovak adaptation of the Negative Act Questionnaire-Revised, developed as part of this study, was administered to nurses, resulting in a final sample of 244 participants. Spearman's correlation and Welch's ANOVA tests analyzed variable relationships using jamovi software.

Results – Nearly one-third of nurses were victims of bullying (32.2%, >45 points), with another third experiencing occasional bullying (32.2%, 33-44 points). The median score per responder was 38 (IQR: 23), with person-related bullying scoring highest (median 19, IQR: 13). Younger nurses with less experience reported higher mobbing levels ($p < 0.001$). Nurses in frontline roles

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(operating rooms, intensive care units, surgical units) experienced significantly more bullying than those in outpatient clinics ($p=0.01$). Doctoral degree holders had the lowest mobbing scores ($p<0.001$), while nurses in frontline roles reported higher mobbing levels than Ward/Charge Nurses ($p<0.001$).

Conclusions – The study highlights a significant correlation between nurses' experiences of mobbing and factors such as age, experience, education, position, and workplace type. The high incidence of bullying among Slovak nurses requires immediate attention from healthcare leaders.

Implications – To address workplace bullying, healthcare institutions should implement zero-tolerance policies, provide ongoing education in professional conduct, emotional intelligence, and conflict resolution, and integrate these topics into nursing curricula. Leadership should model respectful behavior, while mentorship frameworks and resilience training support novice nurses. Finally, accessible reporting systems must ensure accountability.

Key words: workplace bullying, nurses, healthcare work environment, patient safety

**Nurses as School Healthcare Workers in the School Environment in
Slovakia**

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Introduction: This study aims to identify the priority areas of activity for nurses working as school health professionals, with a focus on their preventive, supportive, educational, and counseling roles.

Methodology: A non-standardized online questionnaire was distributed to 12 current and former school health workers in various schools across eastern Slovakia between January and March 2025. The 23-question survey focused on job content, cooperation with school staff and other professionals, common student health issues, working conditions, motivation, and practical obstacles. Descriptive statistics were used to interpret the collected data.

Results: The findings highlight the essential role of school health professionals in caring for chronically ill children, preventing injuries and infectious diseases, and promoting healthy lifestyles among students.

Conclusion: The negative assessments from school health professionals reveal a need for greater systemic support within the profession, highlighting the importance of improved training and raising awareness of the critical value these professionals bring to the school environment.

Key words: nurse, school health worker, competencies, school environment, child

Nutrition, Education and Prevention of Dental Caries in the Context Of Family Health

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Introduction: Dental caries is a multifactorial condition and the most common chronic disease of childhood. It is a diet- and microbiome-related disease in which the composition of the oral microbiome plays a key role. In the presence of dental caries, the oral cavity acts as a microbial reservoir associated with systemic diseases (such as cardiovascular diseases, obesity, and type I diabetes).

Objective: The aim of this study is to highlight the etiological factors of dental caries in the context of the ecological plaque hypothesis and to emphasize the importance of prevention through dietary habit modification and family education.

Methods: The research sample consisted of 165 children aged 5–12 years and their parents. Data collection was carried out using the standardized WHO (2013) Oral Health Questionnaire for Children and Oral Health Questionnaire for Adults, supplemented by non-standardized questionnaires to provide a more comprehensive view of the issue. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 13.0, R software, and Microsoft Office 365 Excel.

Results: Overweight was present in 44.8% and obesity in 14.7% of child respondents, most frequently in the age group 7–12 years. Research over the past decade confirms that excessive consumption of free sugars is a key factor in the development of dental caries. Sweets were consumed daily by 51.5% of children and several times a week by 44.2% of parents. Sugar-sweetened beverages were consumed several times a week by 51.6% of children and 67.4% of parents. Examination of the DMFT index indicated high (20%) and very high (14.5%) caries risk among children aged 5–12 years. DMFT index values had a statistically significant effect on BMI ($P = 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$). Parents who regularly attended dental hygiene visits had a significantly better dental status ($P = 0.0065$).

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Conclusion: The FDI classifies dental caries as a non-communicable, behavior-influenced disease, emphasizing the role of patient behavior in its onset and progression. Regular recall visits in dental hygiene clinics, combined with nutritional counseling, enable the reduction of both the amount and frequency of free sugar intake. Education of parents and children represents an effective preventive strategy against dental caries, with a positive impact not only on oral but also on overall health of both children and their parents.

Key words: Education, Oral health, Prevention, Nutrition, Dental caries.

**Assessment of the Success of Minimally Invasive Lumbar Spine Surgery
Using the ODI Index: A Comparison of Preoperative and Postoperative
Outcomes**

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Introduction: Low back pain represents a major global health issue and is frequently associated with functional impairment and long-term disability. Surgical management is indicated in patients unresponsive to conservative treatment modalities; however, evidence regarding its effect on postoperative disability requires rigorous evaluation.

Objective: The present study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of surgical intervention in reducing functional disability in Polish patients with chronic low back pain, assessed by the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI).

Material and Methods: A cohort of 250 patients undergoing spinal surgery was prospectively evaluated. Each participant completed the standardized ODI questionnaire preoperatively and during postoperative follow-up. All 10 ODI domains—pain intensity, personal care, lifting, walking, sitting, standing, sleeping, sexual activity, social life, and traveling—were analyzed. Statistical significance of change between pre- and postoperative scores was determined using paired Student's *t*-test at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results: Postoperative evaluation demonstrated highly significant improvements across all ODI domains ($p < 0.001$). The most pronounced reduction was observed in pain perception (mean difference -2.72), while the smallest, yet still significant, change was noted in sexual activity (-1.24). Overall, mean ODI decreased by 33.44 percentage points, indicating a substantial decline in disability levels following surgery.

Conclusions: Surgical treatment of chronic low back pain resulted in a clinically and statistically significant reduction of disability across all dimensions of daily living. These findings provide robust evidence supporting surgical intervention as an effective strategy to improve functional status and quality of life in patients with severe spinal disorders.

Key words: neurosurgery, minimal invasive surgery, ODI index.

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**Family and education in health and illness – assessing the infant's
development and meeting their sleep needs**

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Introduction: Parents prefer online sources of information and use white noise to improve the sleep of infants. The aim of the work was to compare the assessments of psychomotor development of children of the selected sample by a nurse using Standard No. 0023 for the examination of psychomotor development of children within the framework of a preventive examination in primary care. Secondly, we mapped the awareness of parents around children's sleep, determined nursing diagnoses NANDA and proposed recommendations based on the EBN principle.

Methods: This cross-sectional descriptive study followed the STROBE guidelines. We used a combination of empirical methods: standardized test for assessing infant psychomotor

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development, meta-analysis, structured interviews with parents, and content analysis of documents. The sample consisted of a total of 36 infants and their parents from 3 pediatric outpatient clinics in Slovakia. We evaluated the data using the score achieved at a significance level of $p = 0.05$. We analyzed studies focused on supporting sleep in infants with white noise.

Results: Parental ratings of infant psychomotor development showed 8.7% variability compared to the standard. The effectiveness of the scale was 96.7% when the child was re-examined. We confirmed the reserves in the awareness of parents of the first child about the sleep regime ($p < 0.05$). The most common source of information was online sources. In the meta-analysis (Prisma), we searched for 81 published sources of evidence on the use of white noise, and recommendations were proposed from 8 sources of evidence.

Conclusion: We confirmed that the nurse can detect deviations in the psychomotor development of the infant in a timely manner and solve problems in satisfying the need for sleep. We recommend that parents use white noise to put the infant to sleep for a brief time of 5-10 minutes with an intensity of 50-55 dB in the sleep phase. We recommend that nurses make the education of mothers more effective through printed educational materials and strengthen the use of telenursing.

Key words: infant, psychomotor development, sleep, white noise.

**Validation and invalidation of Emotions in the Family - Understanding,
Recognizing and Coping with Emotional Dysregulation**

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Introduction: The family constitutes the primary environment for the development of human emotionality. It is within relationships with close relatives that we learn to recognize, express, and modulate emotions. The way family members respond to one another's emotions influences the development of emotional regulation skills and the formation of secure attachment. Emotional validation, understood as acceptance and understanding of another person's emotional experience, strengthens the sense of safety and supports healthy emotional functioning. Emotional invalidation – namely denying, minimizing, or judging emotions – leads instead to emotional dysregulation, manifesting as difficulties in understanding, tolerating, and expressing emotions.

Aim: The aim of the presentation is to deepen the understanding of emotional validation and invalidation in the family context and to identify ways of recognizing and coping with emotional dysregulation. The presentation seeks to demonstrate how emotional messages within the family influence mental health, relationships, and the well-being of its members.

Methods and Materials: The paper is based on a review of the literature in the field of emotion psychology and dialectical behavior therapy (DBT). Clinical and situational examples are presented to illustrate how validation supports emotional co-regulation, while invalidation reinforces patterns of dysregulation. Special attention is given to the distinction between primary emotions (authentic and adaptive) and secondary emotions (reactive and often defensive), which is of key importance in the process of understanding and working with emotions within the family.

Conclusions: The conscious use of emotional validation in family relationships constitutes an important protective factor, promoting emotional regulation, a sense of safety, and psychological well-being. In contrast, emotional invalidation may lead to the consolidation of dysregulatory patterns, emotional disorders, and relational difficulties. Developing skills in recognizing emotions, validating them, and responding constructively to dysregulation is a key element in supporting emotional health and building more empathetic family bonds.

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Digital literacy of seniors and healthcare

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The digital transformation in healthcare is growing into various forms of care provision from telemedicine to mobile applications to electronic health systems. For seniors, as a group with a higher risk of chronic diseases and limited digital skills, the move to a digital environment represents a significant challenge. Nursing, as a profession focused on holistic care and supporting patient self-sufficiency, has an irreplaceable role in the process. Nurses and other healthcare professionals are often the first point of contact, providing not only health but also educational support in the field of digital skills. The aim of the paper is to highlight the need to find effective approaches that would enable seniors to acquire and maintain digital competencies related to healthcare. Such educational and support interventions can improve their self-sufficiency, involvement in decision-making about their own health and prevent risks associated with incorrect or insufficient use of digital resources. This article is part of the

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research project Project no. 002KU-42025 - Digital health literacy of seniors from the perspective of nursing and physiotherapy.

Key words: Literacy, Senior, Health care, Communication, Safety.

**Parents' Knowledge of First Aid for Choking and Sudden Cardiac Arrest
in Children Under 1 Year of Age**

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Introduction. Infant safety is one of the main priorities for parents, especially during the child's first year of life. Although most newborns adapt well to life outside the womb, emergencies – such as choking or sudden cardiac arrest (SCA) – can pose a serious threat. A lack of appropriate knowledge and low self-confidence among parents in such moments often lead to delays or mistakes in providing first aid. Despite the wide availability of information, not all sources are reliable, and relying on knowledge passed on by non-professionals may be incomplete or contain errors. Participation in first aid training conducted by qualified medical personnel enables parents to gain reliable theoretical knowledge and acquire practical skills, resulting in a faster and more effective response in life-threatening situations. Regular participation in such courses reinforces knowledge, develops muscle memory, and builds confidence – crucial factors when acting under stress.

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Aim. The aim of the study was to assess the level of parents' knowledge and their self-assessment regarding the provision of first aid in cases of choking and SCA in children under one year of age, before and after participation in a training course.

Materials and Methods. The study had a prospective-retrospective design. It included parents of children under one year of age and expectant parents. A custom-designed questionnaire was used to assess the participants' level of knowledge, experience, and attitudes, as well as a Likert scale to evaluate their level of self-confidence. Results obtained before and after participation in the first aid training were analyzed.

Results. The largest group consisted of parents aged 30–40 years (74.7%) and individuals with higher education (87.1%). The mean knowledge test score before the training was 23.45 ± 2.34 , while after the training it increased to 27.16 ± 1.11 . This difference was statistically significant ($p \leq 0.05$), confirming the positive impact of training on participants' knowledge and self-assessment.

Conclusions. First aid training significantly increases parents' knowledge and confidence in responding to life-threatening emergencies in infants. The results highlight the need for regular, easily accessible training courses – especially for future and new parents – as an important element of prevention and health education.

Key words: first aid training, infant emergencies, choking, sudden cardiac arrest, parental knowledge, self-confidence

**The role of a health and social worker in a multidisciplinary INTENSIVE
CARE team**

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This paper addresses the integration of health and social workers into multidisciplinary intensive care teams. The role of health and social workers goes beyond traditional social counselling and is becoming increasingly important, particularly in ensuring continuity of care, coordinating follow-up services, and communicating with family and loved ones to facilitate the safe discharge of patients from intensive care to follow-up care in an institutional or home environment.

We also consider the multidimensional nature of health and social workers' interventions, which encompasses socio-economic, psychological, and legal-legislative areas. They also assess the caregiver's ability to provide adequate home care, including demanding tasks such as operating home artificial lung ventilation, managing airway care, and ensuring enteral nutrition.

The absence of health and social workers (HSWs) in intensive care teams reflects the limitations of the current system. We aim to highlight the need to systematically anchor the role of HSWs as coordinators between the health and social spheres. This would contribute to a deeper understanding of the importance of effectively integrating this profession into acute care clinical practice.

Key words: Health and social worker, continuity in intensive care, coordination of services, multidisciplinary.

**Quality of Life in Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease:
Preliminary Findings**

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE "FAMILY – HEALTH – DISEASE"
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Edited by: Luba Ślósarz, Iwona Zborowska, Anna Dąbek, Andrzej Jarynowski, Mariola Seń

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Introduction: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease affects multiple dimensions of life. Advances in modern and effective treatment methods have reduced mortality and extended life expectancy; however, the chronic nature of the disease continues to impact patients' quality of life and emotional well-being.

Objective: The objective of this study was to assess the quality of life and the severity of depression in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease treated with oxygen concentrators and noninvasive mechanical ventilation.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted on a group of 40 men aged 47–85 years (mean age: 68.7 years \pm 8.59 years) treated for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), with a mean disease duration of 6.53 \pm 5.85 years. The participants were divided into two groups. Group I included 20 men treated with an oxygen concentrator, while Group II comprised 20 patients receiving noninvasive mechanical ventilation. Quality of life was assessed using the WHOQOL-BREF and EQ5D-5L questionnaires. The severity of depressive symptoms was evaluated using the Beck Depression Inventory.

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Results: In the group of men treated with an oxygen concentrator, the Beck Depression Inventory score was 11.1 ± 4.34 points, compared to 20.9 ± 13.00 points in the group receiving non-invasive mechanical ventilation, although the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Patients using an oxygen concentrator exhibited significantly higher scores across the somatic, psychological, social, and environmental domains of the WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, overall quality of life, as assessed by the EQ-5D-5L, was higher in the oxygen concentrator group.

Conclusions: Mild depression is present in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, with higher severity among those managed with non-invasive mechanical ventilation. Quality of life is higher in individuals treated with an oxygen concentrator compared to those treated with non-invasive mechanical ventilation.

Key words: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, quality of life, depression, oxygen therapy, noninvasive ventilation

Care for patient with acute lymphoblastic leukaemia

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Introduction: Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL) is the most prevalent childhood malignancy, accounting for 30% of pediatric cancers. Its intensive treatment imposes profound burdens on families, necessitating holistic care approaches.

Purpose of the Work: This case report analyzes the implementation of Family-Centered Care (FCC) for a 14-year-old male, examining family involvement in symptom management during chemotherapy.

Case Report: The description concerns the clinical situation of a 14-year-old male admitted to hospital with high fever and abnormal blood test results. During diagnosis, ALL was confirmed and the boy was qualified for treatment using the protocol ALL IC - 2009. FCC was initiated simultaneously. Key clinical and family dynamics: 1) Complications included neuropathic pain (Visual Analog Scale, VAS: 8/10), nausea, and fungal infections. 2) Family Integration: Mother as primary pain monitor (VAS documentation) and nutrition coordinator; father providing logistic/financial support; sibling engaged via internet connections. 3) Interventions: Gabapentin for neuropathic pain (VAS 8→0), antifungal protocols, and family-led meal planning. Outcomes: No treatment interruptions and reduced hospitalization frequency.

Conclusions:

- 1) FCC enables effective symptom management chemioterapeutic treatment.
- 2) Parent-led monitoring improves adherence.
- 3) Sibling inclusion prevents psychological trauma.
- 4) Protocol adaptation should include mandatory FCC components.

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Key words: Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia (ALL); Family-Centered Care (FCC); pediatric oncology nursing; parental involvement in care; Nursing care in chemotherapy; Role of the nurse in pediatric care

**Childbirth Anxiety and Birth Experience: Analysis of the Relationship
Between Anxiety Level (KLP II) and Maternal Satisfaction (QACE)**

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Background: Childbirth anxiety is an important factor influencing women's perception and satisfaction with labor and delivery. It can affect pain perception, the course of labor, and subsequent evaluation of perinatal experiences. High anxiety levels are associated with a sense of loss of control and an increased need for psychological support.

Aim: The aim of the study was to analyze the relationship between the level of childbirth anxiety (KLP II) and the birth experience assessed using the QACE questionnaire, as well as to identify factors influencing maternal satisfaction.

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Materials and Methods: The study included 111 women with a mean age of 31.8 years. Demographic data, KLP II results, and QACE sections were analyzed. Experiences of women delivering vaginally (VD) and by cesarean section (CS) were compared. Statistical analysis involved Student's *t*/Mann–Whitney tests, ANOVA/Kruskal–Wallis tests, Spearman's correlations, and regression models.

Results: The mean anxiety score was 13.7 points (SD = 3.4); low anxiety was observed in 48.9% of women, and very high anxiety in 13.0%. Groups differed significantly in terms of education level ($p = 0.019$). Birth experiences were generally rated positively—highest for the immediate postpartum period (1.43 ± 0.71) and lowest for retrospective memories (2.92 ± 0.56). The mean global birth rating was 7.03 points (SD = 2.91). Women delivering vaginally rated the first and second stages of labor lower than women after CS ($p < 0.001$), and reported greater pain in the second stage ($p < 0.001$). The global rating was slightly higher in the VD group ($p = 0.067$). Higher anxiety levels correlated with poorer overall birth experience ($\rho = -0.62$), less positive evaluation of the first moments after birth ($\rho = -0.27$), and more negative retrospective memories ($\rho = 0.43$). At the same time, higher anxiety was associated with a better global rating of childbirth ($\rho = 0.44$), which may indicate the important role of staff support in this group of patients. No association was found between anxiety and pain perception. Women with higher anxiety levels more often rated support and communication positively ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Childbirth anxiety significantly affects the birth experience, particularly in the domains of general feelings and retrospective evaluation, which were worse among women with higher anxiety. At the same time, higher anxiety was linked to a better global assessment of childbirth and more positive evaluations of staff support and communication, which may reflect greater intensity of care and support provided to more anxious patients.

Key words: childbirth anxiety; childbirth experience; maternal satisfaction; KLP II; QACE; labor pain; perinatal support; staff communication; vaginal birth; cesarean section

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**Risk Factors for Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia: Perinatal and Neonatal
Analysis**

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Background: Neonatal jaundice is the most common condition in the neonatal period.

Elevated serum bilirubin may result from prematurity, exclusive breastfeeding, infections, and hemolysis due to blood group incompatibility.

Objective: To identify demographic and clinical factors associated with hyperbilirubinemia in neonates, with emphasis on pregnancy course, delivery, and perinatal complications.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was performed using medical records of 414 neonates hospitalized in the Neonatology Department of Stefan Żeromski Specialist Hospital, Kraków (January 2024–March 2025). Data included bilirubin levels, birth weight, gestational age, and perinatal parameters. Statistical analysis employed descriptive measures and graphical presentation (Statistica PL).

Results: Most infants were born vaginally with normal birth weight and high Apgar scores; 42% were exclusively breastfed. Hyperbilirubinemia was more frequent among exclusively breastfed infants, those at the lower end of gestational age, with elevated hematocrit, and in cases of Rh or ABO incompatibility. Vaginal delivery independently increased the need for phototherapy compared with cesarean delivery.

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Conclusions: Lower gestational age, exclusive breastfeeding, elevated hematocrit, maternal Rh-negative status, and vaginal delivery are significant risk factors for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. Hemoglobin and hematocrit may serve as useful prognostic indicators for early identification of neonates at increased risk requiring intervention.

Key words: hyperbilirubinemia, neonatal jaundice, phototherapy

**Adherence to Perinatal Care Standards and Patient Satisfaction in
Different Hospital Wards: A Cross-Sectional Analysis**

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Introduction: Compliance with perinatal care standards is the foundation of safety and quality in medical services and simultaneously affects women's satisfaction with childbirth and their subjective birth experience. Analyzing the relationship between adherence to standards and patient satisfaction makes it possible to identify areas that require special attention in clinical practice.

Aim: The aim of the study was to assess the relationship between adherence to perinatal care standards and patient satisfaction across different hospital wards, as well as their birth experience assessed using the QACE questionnaire.

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Material and Methods: The study included 111 women after childbirth (55 after cesarean section, 56 after vaginal delivery). A questionnaire was used, including demographic data, 39 questions regarding adherence to standards, evaluation of satisfaction in the delivery room, maternity ward, and neonatal ward, as well as the QACE tool (pain assessment and global birth experience). Non-parametric tests (Wilcoxon, Friedman, Mann–Whitney) and Spearman's correlations ($\alpha = 0.05$) were applied.

Results: Patient satisfaction was very high across all wards (mean 1.16–1.19 on a 1–5 scale), with the highest scores in the delivery room and the lowest in the maternity ward. Midwives were rated significantly higher than physicians ($p < 0.001$), highlighting the importance of interpersonal relationships in shaping the birth experience. Adherence to care standards was high (>90%). Particularly positive ratings were given for ensuring privacy, the presence of a companion, rooming-in, and respectful treatment. However, correlation analysis showed that the most crucial factors were: maintaining privacy and dignity ($\rho = -0.70$; $p < 0.01$), clarity of information provided ($\rho = -0.66$; $p < 0.01$), and informing patients about the possibility of submitting feedback ($\rho = -0.66$; $p < 0.01$). In the global birth experience assessment (QACE), women after vaginal delivery reported slightly higher satisfaction (mean 7.5/10) compared to women after cesarean section (mean 6.6/10), although the difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.141$).

Conclusions: Despite very high adherence to standards, the greatest impact on patient satisfaction came from elements related to communication, respect, and personalized care. All three wards received very high ratings, but the delivery room and neonatal ward scored slightly higher than the maternity ward. QACE results suggest that women after vaginal births evaluated their experience somewhat more positively than women after cesarean sections.

Key words: perinatal care standards, patient satisfaction, childbirth experience, QACE, staff communication, patient – staff relationship, patient dignity and privacy, maternity ward, neonatal ward, delivery room, vaginal birth, cesarean section.

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Association between current intensity in transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation and pain severity changes

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Introduction: Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) is a widely used modality in physical medicine for the management of various pain conditions. Despite its long history, the optimal stimulation parameters, particularly current intensity, remain under discussion. This study aimed to compare the analgesic effects of TENS applied at two distinct intensity levels.

Materials and Methods: Patients with spinal pain were randomly allocated to two groups: L and H. In both groups, stimulation parameters were individually tailored. In group L, TENS

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was delivered at an intensity corresponding to a mild tingling sensation. In group H, the highest tolerable intensity was applied. Pain severity was recorded immediately before and after the intervention using a 10-point Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). In group H, correlations between pain change (VAS after – VAS before) and applied current intensity were analysed.

Results: In group L, TENS did not produce a statistically significant reduction in pain severity. In contrast, group H exhibited a significant decrease ($p < 0.001$): one participant (3.7%) reported a 3-point reduction; ten participants (37.0%), a 2-point reduction; eleven participants (40.7%), a 1-point reduction; and five participants (18.5%) experienced no change. In group H, higher current intensity correlated significantly with greater pain relief ($R = -0.48$; $p = 0.011$).

Conclusions: A single TENS application at a mild tingling level, regardless of absolute intensity, did not provide meaningful analgesia. Conversely, stimulation at the highest intensity tolerable for the patient resulted in pain reduction in **81.5%** of participants, with stronger stimulation associated with greater improvement. These findings support the use of maximally tolerated intensity to enhance the immediate analgesic effects of TENS in patients with spinal pain.

Key words: transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), analgesic effect, spinal pain, rehabilitation.

**Knowledge and Attitudes Toward Organ Transplantation Among
Residents of the Zielona Góra District**

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS**

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Introduction: Organ transplantation is a key treatment for end-stage organ failure, yet its success depends on public awareness and willingness to donate. Understanding local knowledge and attitudes supports effective education and improves donation systems.

Aim: To assess knowledge and attitudes toward organ transplantation among residents of the Zielona Góra district and to examine associations with sex, age, education, and place of residence.

Material and Methods: A cross-sectional online survey (Google Forms) was conducted between December 2024 and January 2025 among 142 adults (74.6% women; age 18–73 years). Attitudes were measured on a 5-point Likert scale, and knowledge was assessed with a 10-item

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test (score 0–10; 0–3 low, 4–6 average, 7–10 high). Data were analyzed in MS Excel 365 and STATISTICA 13.3 using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test with Lilliefors correction, the Mann–Whitney U test, and Pearson correlations. Significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Attitudes were highly favorable: 95.8% considered donation ethically right, 85.9% declared post-mortem donation willingness, and 95.8% would donate to relatives. The mean knowledge score was 6.76 ± 1.45 (median = 7), indicating average-to-high awareness. Women more often recognized differences between living and deceased donation and were more aware of presumed consent ($p < 0.05$). Age correlated positively with knowledge and awareness of donation types ($p=0.022$). Higher education was associated with viewing donation as ethically right ($p=0.006$). Place of residence showed no significant effects. Older and better-educated respondents more accurately estimated the number of lives saved and understood donor declarations ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Residents show strong pro-donation attitudes and good knowledge of transplantation. Age and education significantly influence awareness, highlighting the need for targeted education among younger and less-educated groups to translate acceptance into formal donor declarations.

Key words: Organ donation; Public awareness; Transplantation attitudes; Health education

**Knowledge and Empathy Levels Among Nursing Students and Practicing
Nurses: A Comparative Study**

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Introduction: Empathy is a key component of interpersonal communication in nursing, influencing the quality of patient care, professional relationships, and overall satisfaction with work. Both cognitive and affective empathy are crucial in understanding and responding to patients' emotions. However, factors such as workload, burnout, and study-related stress can modify empathy levels throughout a nurse's education and career.

Aim: To compare empathy levels between nursing students and professionally active nurses, considering life satisfaction, financial status, education, and work experience.

Material and Methods: The study included 207 participants: 102 nursing students and 105 practicing nurses from the Lubuskie, Wielkopolskie, and Lower Silesian voivodeships. Data

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were collected using an author-designed questionnaire and the Polish version of the PERTH Empathy Scale (Larionow & Mudło-Głagolska, 2022), which assesses both affective and cognitive empathy across positive and negative emotions. Analyses were conducted in Microsoft Excel 365 and STATISTICA 13.3 using non-parametric tests: Spearman's rho and the Mann–Whitney U test. Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Higher life satisfaction correlated with lower negative-affective empathy ($\rho = -0.287$; $p < 0.05$) and higher positive-affective empathy ($\rho = 0.262$; $p < 0.05$) among nurses. No significant associations were observed between empathy and economic status, work experience, or education among nurses. In students, higher education correlated weakly and inversely with empathy in all subscales ($\rho \approx -0.21$ to -0.33 ; $p < 0.05$). There were no significant differences in total empathy levels between students and nurses ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusions: Empathy among nursing students and nurses appears stable regardless of education level, work experience, or financial status. While life satisfaction is associated with greater positive-affective empathy among nurses, other factors exert minimal influence. Empathy in nursing likely depends more on individual personality traits and motivation to help others than on demographic or occupational variables.

Key words: Empathy; Nursing students; Professional nurses; Life satisfaction

Nursing care for patients with multiple sclerosis in inpatient hospice

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Introduction: Multiple sclerosis is an autoimmune neurodegenerative disease of the central nervous system with an inflammatory character, in which demyelinating lesions form in the brain and spinal cord. This progressive damage to the nervous system is multifocal and disseminated. It is characterized by great diversity in both the course of the disease and its symptoms, and can lead to physical disability, cognitive impairment, and a reduced quality of life.

Aim of the study: The aim of the study was to present nursing care for a patient with multiple sclerosis under the care of an inpatient hospice. An attempt was made to identify nursing, communication, and social problems, as well as to implement measures aimed at eliminating them and, consequently, improving the quality of life.

Material: The study used the individual case method. Information on the patient's health status was obtained from observation, interview, physical examination, and analysis of medical records. The following research tools were also used: the Barthel Scale, the Norton Pressure Ulcer Risk Scale, and the Kurtz Mobility Scale (EDSS scale).

Case description: A 51-year-old woman who has been suffering from multiple sclerosis since 1999. In 2015, she experienced visible progression of the disease. The patient was hospitalized several times in the neurology ward due to exacerbations of relapsing-remitting MS. Over time, the relapsing-remitting form transformed into a secondary progressive form, rapidly increasing motor impairment. Currently, the woman is bedridden with spastic quadriplegia and is staying in a stationary hospice. Since 2023, she has been fed through a percutaneous feeding

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gastrostomy. The patient shows signs of dementia. She is able to communicate verbally. On the day of the examination, she scored 0 points on the Barthel scale (requires constant care), 6 points on the Norton scale (high risk of bedsores), and 9.5 points on the Kurtze scale (unable to function and move independently).

Conclusions: Nursing care for a patient with multiple sclerosis in hospice care requires openness, understanding, and acceptance in interpersonal communication, constant assessment of mental and physical condition, and interpretation of current needs. The implementation of early nursing interventions improves the quality of life and, as a consequence, rationalises the physical, mental, social and spiritual condition. Involving family and loved ones in education and the therapeutic process helps in the acceptance of the disease.

Key words: multiple sclerosis, nursing problems, hospice.

Marta Bernat, Sylwia Krzemińska: Communication models in nurse-patient relationships and their impact on patient safety

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Introduction: Communication in the nurse-patient relations is not only about exchanging information, but also about building trust, providing emotional support, and ensuring safety. In the context of healthcare, effective communication can prevent medical errors, increase adherence to treatment recommendations, and improve the patient's quality of life.

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Aim: The aim of this study is to present various models of nurse-patient-family relationships, emphasizing the family as a real partner in medical care and healthcare.

Materials and Methods: The research method was a critical content analysis of publications on the above topic discussing the functioning of patients and families in situations of illness and disability, as well as nurses' communication competencies. Results: Four models of the nurse-patient-family relationship were discussed, ranging from the transmission model, which completely ignores collaboration with the patient and family, through the interactional and transactional model, to the partnership model.

A holistic model of medicine and a systems approach to healthcare require a new approach to nurse education and a new vision of their role. Nurses should fulfill educational, advisory, and consultative roles and serve as medical guides for the patient and family in health-related tasks. In the case of acute conditions and health threats, they should act as advisors and experts within the therapeutic team, based on their competencies.

Conclusions: Choosing the appropriate communication model depends on the clinical situation, the patient's condition, and the nurse's competencies. Communication based on empathy, openness, and a partnership approach yields the best results. Good nurse-patient relationships are the foundation of effective healthcare.

Key words: nurse, patient, family, communication

The occurrence of frailty syndrome and quality of life in chronically ill patients treated at a cardiology clinic

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Introduction: The pathophysiology of frailty syndrome (FS) results primarily from metabolic imbalance and impaired functioning of the immune and endocrine systems. Disturbed cellular processes influence the development of frailty syndrome through changes in the functioning of organs and systems. It should be emphasized that frailty syndrome (FS) is not synonymous with the natural aging process. It can occur both earlier and later than typical old age. Frailty is increasingly recognized as an important and common geriatric syndrome. It is defined as a state of extreme susceptibility to endogenous and exogenous stressors leading to an increased risk of negative health outcomes, including falls, hospitalization, institutionalization, and mortality.

Objective: To demonstrate the relationship between the occurrence of frailty syndrome and the quality of life of chronically ill patients treated at a cardiology clinic.

Material and methods: The study was conducted among 147 patients of a selected cardiology clinic in Mszana Dolna. It was carried out using a diagnostic survey method with tools such as the Edmonton Frailty Scale questionnaire, the Yesavage Depression Scale – 15-point version, and the SF-36 Quality of Life Questionnaire. Statistical analysis was performed using the Chi² test and Spearman's rank correlation, assuming a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results: The collected data enabled the assessment of the relationship between the level of frailty and the quality of life of patients in outpatient specialist care. Patients of the cardiology

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clinic show symptoms of frailty syndrome (FS) of varying severity (59.0%), which confirms the diversity of functional status in this group of patients. A significant correlation was found between the severity of FS and quality of life – the higher the level of frailty syndrome, the lower the subjectively assessed quality of life in terms of both physical and mental functioning ($p = 0.001$). The occurrence of frailty syndrome correlates significantly with increasing patient age ($p < 0.015$) and the number of medications taken ($p = 0.001$), which may indicate the importance of multimorbidity and polypharmacy as risk factors for FS. No significant association was found between FS and the severity of depressive symptoms, although approximately 28% of the study participants were found to have moderate or severe depressive symptoms.

Conclusions: The results obtained indicate the important role of early diagnosis of frailty syndrome and the need to implement measures tailored to the needs of chronically ill patients, especially those receiving cardiac care. The research tools used proved effective in assessing the severity of FS in everyday clinical practice, and the conclusions of the study may serve as a starting point for further analysis and improvement of care for older people undergoing treatment for cardiovascular diseases.

Key words: frailty syndrome, quality of life, polypharmacy, multimorbidity, depression, outpatient specialist care

**Assessment of health behaviors and quality of life in patients with lower
limb arterial occlusion**

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Introduction: Atherosclerosis is a disease of civilization. It involves the formation of atherosclerotic plaque on the walls of arteries, narrowing their lumen. Lower limb ischemia is a condition in which insufficient oxygen is supplied to the tissues of the lower limbs because of impaired blood flow in the arteries. The main risk factors for the development of chronic lower limb ischemia are the same as for atherosclerosis of other arteries, namely: age, gender, diabetes, hypertension, smoking, lipid metabolism disorders, obesity, genetic factors, low physical activity, poor diet, alcohol consumption, stress, and infections.

Methodology: The aim of this study was to examine selected aspects of health, lifestyle, and quality of life in patients with lower limb arterial occlusion. To achieve the research objectives, a diagnostic survey was conducted using research tools such as the WHOQOL-BREF quality of life questionnaire, Health Behavior Inventory, Fagerström test, and a self-designed questionnaire. The study involved 118 participants, including 71 men and 47 women with lower limb arterial occlusion hospitalized at the Department of General and Transplant Surgery at the Jan Mikulicz Radecki University Clinical Hospital in Wrocław, who were qualified for surgery to restore circulation in the limb.

Conclusions: Among patients with lower limb arterial occlusion, the dominant group is the geriatric population (71-80 years old). The quality of life of patients with lower limb arterial occlusion was moderate, with environmental aspects rated highest and social relationships

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lowest. Patients with lower limb arterial occlusion show nicotine dependence in both the mental and physical spheres.

Key words: atherosclerosis, lower limb arterial obstruction, quality of life, health behaviours

Caring for a patient with Parkinson's syndrome in the home environment

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Introduction: Parkinson's syndrome is a set of symptoms of non-idiopathic origin associated with various neurological disorders. Similar to Parkinson's disease, it is characterized by both

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motor and non-motor symptoms that significantly affect quality of life. Treatment focuses mainly on alleviating symptoms, and the most commonly used drug is levodopa.

Material and methods: The nursing process of an 83-year-old patient diagnosed with Parkinson's syndrome at the age of 80 is presented. Data collection included an interview with the patient and his family, direct observation, analysis of medical records, physical measurements, and standardized assessment scales (VES-13, NRS, ADL, and Tinetti).

Results: The primary nursing problems identified were associated with motor, autonomic, and psychological disorders. Nursing interventions focused on pain management, prevention of constipation and falls, enhancement of sleep quality, skin hygiene, support of social interaction, and reduction of anxiety.

Conclusions: Nursing care for patients with Parkinson's syndrome requires an individualized and comprehensive approach. Holistic nursing interventions play a crucial role in improving quality of life and minimizing the risk of complications.

Key words: Parkinson's syndrome, nursing care, quality of life, geriatric assessment

**Quality of life of children with inflammatory bowel disease and the impact
of the disease on family functioning**

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Introduction: Ulcerative colitis (UC) and Crohn's disease (CD) are among the most common inflammatory bowel diseases. These syndromes are rare and mainly affect the adult population. Acceptance of the disease and support from loved ones has a significant impact on the quality of life of patients. The occurrence of a chronic disease in children has a significant impact on intra-family relationships

Aim of work: The aim of the study is to assess the quality of life of children suffering from inflammatory diseases and to indicate the influence of the disease on the functioning of the family.

Methods: The study was carried out by the method of a diagnostic survey with the use of the questionnaire and interview technique. The study used a socio-demographic-clinical questionnaire of its own authorship and standardized IMPACT III and PedsQL questionnaires. 31 children and 31 parents participated in the study. The survey questionnaire was made available in electronic form.

Results: In the studied group, there is a significant relationship between the quality of life of children and the incidence of comorbidities, as there is a significant relationship between the impact of the disease on the family and the incidence of comorbidities. The research analysis confirmed the correlation between the quality of life of children and the impact of the disease on the family. In addition, there is a significant relationship between feeling good and being in remission.

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Conclusions: Additional comorbidities significantly reduce the quality of life of children suffering from inflammatory bowel diseases. The quality of relationships built by relatives interacts on many levels of everyday life. The period of remission has a positive effect on the child's condition at every level of his life, which translates into the functioning of the family. Children as well as their loved ones require comprehensive care based on a holistic view.

Key words: Crohn disease, UC, IBD, pediatrics, quality of life, family functioning.

**Three-Dimensional Gait Analysis in the Evaluation of Physiotherapy after
Eversion Ankle Sprain: A Case Study**

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Introduction: Ankle sprain is one of the most common musculoskeletal injuries. The eversion mechanism, although relatively rare, is clinically more complex and often associated with prolonged recovery. Untreated or improperly managed sprains may lead to reduced mobility, persistent pain, and gait disturbances. Modern diagnostic tools, such as three-dimensional gait analysis, allow objective assessment of functional impairments and monitoring of rehabilitation outcomes.

Aim: The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of a physiotherapy program in a patient after an eversion ankle sprain, using three-dimensional gait analysis to assess biomechanical changes.

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Materials and Methods: The study was conducted at "OrtheoClinic" in Kraków between June 2024 and January 2025. The participant was a 38-year-old physically active female who sustained a right ankle eversion sprain while playing tennis. Two assessment sessions were performed: the first one week after the injury and the second after completion of a 20-week physiotherapy program. The intervention included lymphatic drainage, gait re-education, manual therapy, stabilization and proprioceptive training, and progressive functional loading. Gait parameters were assessed using the Qualisys motion analysis system, and pain intensity was measured with the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS).

Results: Following rehabilitation, clinically meaningful improvements were observed: increased ankle and knee joint range of motion, longer step length, higher cadence, shorter step time and stance phase duration, as well as reduced pain. Although the results did not reach statistical significance ($p>0.05$), they clearly indicated a beneficial effect of the physiotherapy program and functional improvement in gait pattern.

Conclusions: A structured physiotherapy program after eversion ankle sprain enhances lower limb function, reduces pain, and contributes to gait normalization. Three-dimensional gait analysis provides an objective and valuable tool for monitoring rehabilitation outcomes and supporting clinical decision-making.

**Beliefs about Medicines and the Level of Intentional Non-Adherence to
Treatment among Patients with Multiple Sclerosis**

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Introduction: Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory, demyelinating and neurodegenerative disease of the central nervous system. MS has no curable disease but drug modifying therapy (DMT) can delay the long-term disability progression of the disease. The effectiveness of MS treatment depends on the patient's adherence to therapy.

Objective This study evaluated the level of intentional non-adherence and the relationship between beliefs about medication and the level of intentional non-adherence to treatment of patients with multiple sclerosis.

Material and methods: A group of 146 patients with relapsing – remitting MS were included. To assess different aspect of adherence, the Intentional Non-Adherence Scale (INAS) was used. For evaluating patients' beliefs and opinions regarding medication, the Beliefs about Medicines Questionnaire (BMQ) was used.

Results: The mean total INAS score was 51.41 ± 27.83 points. Patients were most concerned about the necessity to take medication and least concerned about the harm caused by medication. The overuse and harm domains of the BMQ were significantly correlated with INAS scores ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: Independent determinant of intentional non-adherence was overuse.

Key words: multiple sclerosis, treatment adherence, disease – modifying therapy, beliefs about medicine

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Breastfeeding and Sustainability

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Introduction: Breastfeeding is not only the optimal method of infant nutrition with long-term positive effects on the health of both mother and child. It is also a highly sustainable form of infant feeding, bringing significant benefits for the environment and society. A breastfeeding mother is not dependent on the production of formula, minimizes energy consumption, saves water, produces no waste, and prevents food loss. Breastfeeding can be fully satisfactory for both mother and child and forms the basis of sustainable healthcare.

Aim: The aim of this review study was to analyze the latest evidence on the relationship between breastfeeding and sustainability and to demonstrate how breastfeeding support can contribute to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to environmentally responsible healthcare practice.

Methods: Based on a search strategy in the databases PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and CINAHL for the period 2010–2025, publications relevant to the research question “*What are the latest findings on breastfeeding and sustainability?*” were identified. The search was conducted using keywords derived from the PICO framework and combined with Boolean operators. The analytical review was carried out following the PRISMA protocol.

Results: Breastfeeding contributes to sustainability primarily through the absence of industrial processes, manufacturing resources, and plastic packaging, which significantly reduces the carbon footprint. At the same time, it promotes population health and reduces the economic burden on healthcare systems. The reviewed studies show that breastfeeding support is consistent with the SDGs, particularly in the areas of good health and well-being (SDG 3), responsible consumption and production (SDG 12), and climate action (SDG 13). An important

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role is played by healthcare professionals, especially midwives, who can educate and support mothers in choosing breastfeeding as an environmentally responsible practice.

Conclusion: Breastfeeding represents a sustainable mode of infant feeding with significant health, economic, and environmental benefits. Its promotion should be an integral part of strategies aimed at sustainable healthcare. This review confirms the importance of linking breastfeeding support with the Sustainable Development Goals, which has crucial implications for clinical practice and public health.

Key words: breastfeeding, sustainability, Sustainable Development Goals, review study, public health

Nursing care for an elderly patient with Parkinson's disease

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Introduction. Parkinson's disease is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder classified as an idiopathic parkinsonian syndrome. Its main symptoms include tremor, muscle stiffness, and slowed movement, leading to significant functional impairment in patients.

Materials and methods. The case of a 78-year-old man who had been suffering from Parkinson's disease since 2013 was analyzed. The data necessary to develop the nursing process were collected based on an interview, observation, analysis of medical records, and standardized questionnaires scale (Tinetti, MMSE, Barthel, CSI, depression scale Beck).

Results. The primary nursing problems were identified, and a holistic nursing care plan was developed, covering biological, psychological, and social issues. The measures taken contributed to a partial improvement in the patient's daily functioning and alleviated the symptoms associated with the disease.

Conclusions.

1. Effective nursing care for a person with Parkinson's disease requires holistic planning and implementation of interventions.
2. Parkinson's disease negatively affects all aspects of the patient's life.
3. Caring for a patient with this condition is a significant challenge for the family.

Key words: Parkinson's disease, nursing care, elderly patient.

Nursing care of a patient in remission from primary fallopian tube cancer

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Introduction: Primary fallopian tube cancer (PFTC) is a rare gynecologic malignancy that tends to disseminate within the abdominal and thoracic cavities. Its most common clinical manifestations include abdominal pain and postmenopausal bleeding, which significantly impair quality of life. The disease occurs predominantly in women with genetic predispositions. Standard treatment consists of hysterectomy, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, all of which carry a considerable risk of complications.

Materials and Methods: The study aimed to develop a nursing care plan focused on enhancing the comfort of a patient in PFTC remission. The nursing care process of an 82-year-old woman was developed based on a patient interview, direct observation, review of medical records, and relevant literature. To assess the patient's condition, the Barthel Index, Tinetti Test, MMSE, VAS, and a psychological support evaluation were applied.

Results: The main nursing problems identified included risk of pulmonary embolism, nausea, dizziness, as well as anxiety and depressed mood related to therapy.

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Conclusions: The nursing care process for a patient in remission from PFTC contributes to improved health outcomes and quality of life. Critical elements include continuous monitoring for potential complications, timely response to clinical deterioration, and provision of psychological support and family education.

Key words: primary fallopian tube cancer, nursing care, remission, quality of life

Health behaviors, knowledge, and educational expectations of pregnant women regarding hypertension during pregnancy

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Introduction: Hypertension during pregnancy is one of the most common obstetric complications, increasing the risk of preeclampsia, cardiovascular complications, and maternal and fetal death. Health behaviors of pregnant women are crucial in preventing diseases and reducing the effects of illness. Education of women in Family Planning Clinics by midwives should include various forms of individual and group education, workshop methods, depending

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on the level of women's knowledge. Midwives should teach self-control and self-observation, especially in the group of women with a family history of hypertension.

Objective: Evaluation of health behaviors, level of knowledge, and educational expectations of pregnant women regarding pregnancy-induced hypertension.

Materials and methods: The study was conducted among 147 female patients of the Sonokard Medical Center in Wrocław with diagnosed chronic or gestational hypertension. A proprietary sociodemographic survey and the standardized Health Behavior Inventory (HBI) by Z. Jurczyński, which includes four categories: proper eating habits, preventive behaviors, positive mental attitude, and health practices, were used. Statistical analyses were performed using the χ^2 test, ANOVA analysis, and Kruskal-Wallis test at the significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Case report: The average overall intensity of health behaviors was 89.2 ± 13.6 points (6.2 sten), which corresponds to a high average level of health behaviors.

Education, place of residence, and marital status did not significantly differentiate the intensity of health behaviors.

Significant correlations were shown between the level of health behaviors and the age of the patients, as well as the categories of health behaviors: proper eating habits, preventive behaviors, positive mental attitude, and health practices.

A higher level of knowledge about hypertension correlated with more frequent adoption of proper health-promoting actions ($p = 0.0012$). Women with higher education are more likely to expect education on thematic workshops on the prevention of hypertension.

Conclusions:

- The level of health behaviors among the women in the study reaches a high average value, which can be increased through education using various workshop methods.
- The age and level of knowledge of the women surveyed significantly influence the frequency of pro-health activities.

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- Medical education should include proper eating habits, blood pressure measurement techniques, and lifestyle modification strategies, and midwives play a key role in implementing this.

Key words: hypertension, pregnancy, healthy behaviors, prevention, health education.

Personal observations from the ‘Personal Assistant for People with Disabilities’ project and the ‘Respite Care’ project

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Introduction: Since 2019, the city of Wrocław has been implementing a social support project in the form of personal assistance and respite care.

The aim of the project is to improve the quality of life of people with disabilities, relieve their carers and enable them to participate in social and professional life.

Development: Working in the field of care and support for people with disabilities, I had the opportunity to work with clients of various ages, from 3 to 24 years old, and with very diverse needs: from mild intellectual disabilities to profound intellectual disabilities and physical disabilities. Participating in the project allowed me to better understand the needs of people with disabilities and their families, as well as to appreciate the importance of even small forms of support. Each day brought new challenges, but also moments of reflection, understanding

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and great emotion. One of the most important elements of my work turned out to be establishing a genuine, sincere relationship with the person I was caring for. Trust requires time, consistency in action, attentive listening and showing respect. I noticed that people with disabilities particularly appreciate authenticity. They do not need pity, but a partnership approach and to be treated with dignity. For me, being an assistant is not only about supporting them in their daily activities, but also about talking, being present and providing a sense of security on a daily basis.

Summary: The greatest value of both projects was to relieve parents and carers of children with disabilities in their daily duties. Parents of children with disabilities particularly appreciated the opportunity to devote time exclusively to themselves, to go out for coffee, shopping, a walk or simply to rest in peace and quiet. Respite care was a real mental and physical support for them, allowing them to recharge their batteries. They often emphasised that such time was rare and a great luxury for them. From the perspective of the children participating in the project, they gained not only care, but also the opportunity to actively explore the world. Families quickly become attached to the support person. In many cases, I was treated like a member of the family with great trust and gratitude. Despite their limitations, the children were able to bring me a lot of joy and teach me to look at the world in a simple, sincere way.

Key words: personal assistant, persons with disabilities

Quality of life and acceptance of the condition in families and children with congenital pigmented nevi or vascular malformations

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Introduction: The presence of a giant pigmented nevus and vascular malformation disturbs the child's perception of their own appearance. People with these conditions feel less accepted by society and encounter difficulties in functioning in the psychological, social and emotional spheres. Aim. The main aim of the study was to assess the quality of life and acceptance of the condition in families and children with congenital pigmented nevi or vascular malformations.

Material and methods: The study was conducted using a diagnostic survey method. The study used an original socio-demographic questionnaire and a standardised questionnaire for assessing quality of life – PedsQL. The study was conducted using a Google form with complete anonymity. The study group consisted of 100 respondents: children aged 0-25 years with congenital pigmented nevi or vascular malformations and their parents. The study lasted 6 months. Results. The diversity of skin lesions determines various directions of treatment and care for the child. Undoubtedly, quality of life and acceptance of the disease situation are becoming a focus of interest for researchers. Many variables that influence the subjective assessment of quality of life, such as the patient's age, the extent of the lesion, place of residence,

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and family financial status, determine the results. Quality of life changes during the treatment process, so it is difficult to define it unambiguously. Age is a factor that determines functioning in the emotional, physical and social spheres. Families did not define the disease as having an impact on family functioning, but focused on the negative perception by society and the lack of knowledge and information. Conclusions: 1. The child's disease does not significantly affect family functioning. 2. Public awareness of pigmented nevi and vascular malformations is low. 3. The age of the child affects the acceptance of the disease; older children show poorer functioning in the social sphere. 4. The older the parent, the lower the child's quality of life in the physical, cognitive, emotional and social spheres.

Key words: quality of life, children, vascular malformations

Care for a senior with multiple illnesses – a case study

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Introduction: As we age, the body's ability to maintain homeostasis declines, and the deterioration of one organ can lead to dysfunction in another: this domino effect is characteristic

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of geriatric patients. A minor health problem can trigger further ailments, ultimately leading to disability in patients over 65. Multimorbidity results in numerous and burdensome health problems that patients must contend with in their daily lives.

Objective: The aim of the study was to assess the patient's health status, identify nursing problems, and develop a nursing care plan for a geriatric patient with multimorbidity.

Material and Methods: The study was based on an individual case study using interviews, medical records, and measurements of vital signs and anthropometrics. The Tinetti test and Barthel scale were used. The NRS scale was used to assess pain intensity. The Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) was also used.

Conclusions: After conducting an interview and a comprehensive assessment of the patient, the main nursing challenges faced by the patient and the nursing staff were identified. These included: risk of falls, poor tolerance of physical activity due to circulatory failure, post-fracture hip pain, loss of appetite, depression, and insomnia. This allowed for the development of an individualized nursing care plan, taking into account the patient's bio-psycho-social status.

Key words: aging, multimorbidity, care.

Loneliness among seniors in Poland

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**INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE "FAMILY – HEALTH – DISEASE"
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS**

Edited by: Luba Ślósarz, Iwona Zborowska, Anna Dąbek, Andrzej Jarynowski, Mariola Seń

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Introduction: Loneliness is an emotional state resulting from a lack of belonging, interpersonal relationships, and support. It can affect people at any stage of life or age. The aging population and limited mental and physical abilities mean that older people increasingly experience social isolation. This can stem from various causes, such as health problems, the loss of a spouse, social exclusion, living alone, or reduced social contacts.

This article will explore the topic of loneliness and analyze the causes, effects, and importance of interventions and preventative measures in preventing loneliness among older adults.

Keywords: loneliness, older adults

Nursing care for a patient with prostate cancer

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Introduction: Prostate cancer is one of the most commonly diagnosed cancers in men. Its exact causes have not yet been clearly identified, but risk factors include age over 65, genetic predisposition, poor diet, lack of physical activity, smoking, and obesity. Diagnosis is primarily based on PSA levels, digital rectal examination, and imaging studies. Treatment is tailored to the individual case and may include surgery, hormonal therapy, or chemotherapy.

Aim of the study: The aim of the study was to assess the patient's health status, identify nursing problems and develop a nursing care plan for a patient with prostate cancer.

Subject of study: The subject of this study is nursing care for patients with prostate cancer, the development of an individualized care plan, the assessment of the patient's quality of life, and the effectiveness of nursing interventions. The nursing process presented in this study was developed according to Dorothea Orem's nursing model, which is based on the assumption that nursing interventions are necessary when an individual experiences limitation in their ability to self-care and is unable to fully meet their health needs.

Research method and techniques: The study was based on a review of the latest publicly available literature, a patient interview, observations, and analysis of medical records provided by the patient. Additional tools used in the study included an interview questionnaire, the VES-13 scale, the Nutritional Risk Screening (NRS) 2002 scale, the COPD Assessment Test (CAT) scale, the Numerical Rating Scale, the Barthel scale, the Beck Depression Inventory, and the Tinetti scale.

Conclusions: Following an interview and comprehensive assessment of the patient, the main nursing challenges faced by the patient and the nursing staff were identified. These included weaknesses, pain, decreased physical activity, risk of malnutrition, and depression. Based on these findings, an individual nursing care plan was developed, incorporating bio-psycho-social support. Nursing care for the patient includes systematic monitoring and assessment of the

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severity of disease symptoms. Providing support in daily activities and education about the disease and a healthy lifestyle enables the patient to follow recommendations and take care of their health, which positively impacts treatment outcomes.

Key words: prostate cancer, nursing care, COPD, depression

Stress, mental health and academic burnout among students

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Introduction: Academic burnout increasingly affects students, leading to decreased motivation, exhaustion and mental health problems.

Material and methods: The study included 168 nursing and obstetrics students in their final year of undergraduate and postgraduate studies at the Medical University of Wrocław. Data were collected using questionnaires. Three tools were used: the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for Students (OLBI-S), the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) and the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), as well as an original questionnaire.

Results: The highest level of academic burnout was observed among students aged 20–22 and third-year undergraduate students. An important predictor of academic burnout was stress related to a large number of classes, the strictness of academic staff, and family pressure.

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Younger students were more likely to seek psychological help. High levels of stress correlated with deteriorating mental health.

Conclusions: Academic burnout is a common phenomenon at universities, especially among younger students. The results indicate a need for preventive measures and psychological support in the academic environment.

Key words: academic burnout, stress, depressive disorders.

**Assessment of functional capacity, life satisfaction and occurrence of
depression among geriatric patients**

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Introduction: The ageing process is a natural stage of human life, characterised by a gradual decline in the physical and functional capacity of the body. As a result of these changes, an individual's quality of functioning and satisfaction with life are reduced over time.

Material and methods: A total of 110 patients consisting of 79 (72%) women and 31 (28%) men of geriatric age, hospitalised in the Department of Internal Medicine and Geriatrics, were included in the study. The following questionnaire-based research tools were used: a self-

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administered sociodemographic and clinical data questionnaire, the ADL Scale, the SWLS Scale and the GDS Scale.

Results: The respondents' assessment of their functional capacity appeared to be statistically dependent on the gender and age of the patients, as well as on the number of chronic diseases they were diagnosed with, the daily number of medications they were constantly taking, and their self-assessment of satisfaction with their health. Satisfaction with life and respondents' level of depression correlated slightly or not significantly statistically with all study variables.

Conclusions: Male gender and age > 80 years predispose to significant disability on the ADL scale. As the degree of functional capacity of the subjects increases, the number of diagnosed chronic diseases and the daily number of medications they continuously take decrease. In contrast, self-rated satisfaction with their health increases. As the degree of depression increases, the functional capacity and life satisfaction of the respondents decreases. The number of diagnosed chronic illnesses and medications taken increases as the degree of depression increases and the degree of functional capacity and life satisfaction of geriatric respondents decreases.

Key words: geriatric age, life satisfaction, old age depression, functional capacity.

Quality of life patients with Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH)

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Introduction: An enlarged prostate, especially benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), can significantly reduce the quality- of- life patients. By far the biggest problems are related to urination. Difficulty in urination, too frequent urge to urinate (especially nocturia) and a feeling of incomplete emptying of the bladder may lead to discomfort, social isolation, reduced

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physical efficiency and consequently, to mental disorders. In advanced cases, untreated BPH can lead to bladder infections, urolithiasis and in the end stage, kidney failure.

Objective: The aim of the study was to answer the question how benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) affects the quality- of -life patients with this disease defined in this way.

Materials and Methods: The study involved 103 men diagnosed with benign prostatic hyperplasia. The study was voluntary and was conducted in the form of an anonymous survey placed on a social networking site in closed groups related to the disease entity. The survey among patients was conducted using the diagnostic survey method using two standardized research tools: the IPSS survey, the SF-36 questionnaire, and a self-reported survey.

Conclusions: Severe symptoms of the disease, duration of the disease, and the age of patients influence the quality of life of respondents.

Key words: benign prostatic hyperplasia, prostate, BPH, LUTS, IPSS, SF-36, quality of life

**Care for patients with chronic wounds resulting from undifferentiated
connective tissue disease**

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Introduction: Connective tissue diseases (CTD) are a group of autoimmune diseases that affect the body's connective tissues, including joints, muscles, skin, blood vessels, lungs, and kidneys. CTD is characterized by vague symptoms that may include fatigue, joint pain, muscle pain, weakness, skin rashes, and breathing difficulties. CTD is a chronic condition, and treatment involves relieving symptoms, controlling the disease, and preventing complications. Undifferentiated connective tissue disease (UCTD) is a form of CTD that does not fit into a specific type of CTD because symptoms and laboratory results are vague or incomplete. Treatment for UCTD involves relieving symptoms and monitoring the disease to avoid serious complications.

Aim of the study: The aim of this study was to present the nurse's role in the comprehensive care of individuals with chronic wounds resulting from undifferentiated connective tissue disease. Particular attention was paid to nursing interventions in the prevention and treatment of infections, wound care, and achieving and maintaining the patient's good psychophysical condition.

Subject of study: The subject of this study is the holistic therapeutic and care process for individuals with undifferentiated connective tissue disease, who developed chronic wounds during the course of the disease. This study utilizes Callista Roy's nursing theory. The nurse should help the patient adapt to changes occurring in many areas of their life. This is particularly important in connective tissue diseases, as they dramatically alter the patient's comfort and quality of life.

Research method and techniques: The study involved a woman with undifferentiated connective tissue disease (UCTD) using an individual case study approach presented through the nursing process. The study utilized an interview questionnaire, medical records analysis, the NRS Pain Scale, the Beck Depression Inventory, the Functional Independence Measurement Chart (FIM) with additional information for the modified functional independence measurement chart template, the ACDS Adherence in Chronic Diseases Scale,

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the WAR Wound Infection Risk Assessment Scale, the NRS 2002 Malnutrition Risk Assessment Scale, the Barthel Scale, the Norton Scale, and the AIS Acceptance of Illness Scale.

Conclusions: Nursing problems experienced by patients with UCTD are diverse due to the wide range of possible symptoms. The most common include deficits in self-care resulting from immobilization or limited independence, increased risk of infection, joint pain, skin rashes, fatigue, digestive problems, difficulties with vascular cannulation, thrombosis, and low mood caused by the chronic condition. The key goal of nursing care is to improve the patient's quality of life across all functional areas. Individuals with this condition often have limited self-care and mobility, so the nurse's role is to assist in meeting hygiene needs and counteracting joint contractures through patient activation. The nurse should provide psychological support to the patient, as, alongside family, they have the most frequent and closest contact with the patient, allowing them to most quickly detect changes in the patient's mental state and respond promptly.

Key words: undifferentiated connective tissue disease, chronic wounds, nursing

**Implementation of Immunization Programs in Poland and Europe, 2020–
2025: Public Health Lessons for the Post-Pandemic Era**

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Background: Between 2020 and 2025, European immunization programmes faced unprecedented disruptions due to COVID-19 while simultaneously launching mass vaccination campaigns.

Objective: To review the implementation of routine and COVID-19 vaccinations in Poland and Europe, focusing on programme changes, coverage, inequities, recovery actions and future priorities.

Methods: Narrative review of PubMed and grey-literature sources from ECDC, WHO/Europe, the European Commission and Poland's NIZP PZH-PIB (2020–2025).

Results: The EU Vaccines Strategy (June 2020) enabled rapid COVID-19 roll-out, yet routine uptake declined, especially MMR and influenza. In Poland, vaccine refusals increased and timeliness dropped, although a free nationwide HPV programme for 12–13-year-olds began in 2023 and the 2025 schedule includes catch-up elements. In 2024, the WHO European Region recorded the highest measles burden since 1997, exposing immunity gaps.

Conclusions: Sustained catch-up, service re-design (including community pharmacy delivery), evidence-based communication against misinformation, and robust financing/monitoring are required to restore high coverage.

Key words: immunization coverage; measles resurgence; HPV programme; EU Vaccines Strategy.

**Nurses' Knowledge of Contact-Transmitted Healthcare-Associated
Infections: A Cross-Sectional Study Based on WHO Guidelines**

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Background: Contact-transmitted healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) remain a major patient-safety challenge; strict adherence to hand hygiene and aseptic procedures by nursing staff is crucial.

Aim: To assess nurses' knowledge of contact-transmitted infections and identify demographic and professional factors differentiating results (age, education, length of service, ward profile, work system).

Material and methods: A cross-sectional questionnaire survey was conducted among 108 respondents (99.1% women) employed on surgical and medical wards; most worked shifts (78.7%). A custom 26-item knowledge questionnaire (primarily true/false), developed on the basis of WHO recommendations, and a demographic form were used. Scale reliability: Cronbach's $\alpha=0.684$. Analyses: Shapiro–Wilk, Mann–Whitney U, Kruskal–Wallis with Dunn's post hoc test, and Fisher's exact test; $p<0.05$.

Results: The mean number of correct responses was 26.9 ± 2.5 (range 15–31). For 16/31 items, $\geq 95\%$ of answers were correct; the weakest performance concerned item 5 (47.2% correct). The highest proportion of correct answers was noted for items 7 and 25-1 (100%). Age differentiated knowledge: participants ≥ 51 years scored lower than those ≤ 40 years ($p=0.012$). Higher

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education was associated with a slightly better total score ($p=0.048$), while ≥ 31 years of service corresponded to lower scores compared with ≤ 20 years ($p=0.023$). No significant differences were found between ward types or work systems for most items.

Conclusions: Overall nurses' knowledge of contact-transmitted HAIs is high, yet thematic gaps persist, with declines in the oldest age groups and among those with very long tenure. Regular WHO-based training is recommended, targeted to weaker areas and supported by strategies to reinforce hand-hygiene habits across teams.

Key words: healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), contact transmission, hand hygiene.

Occupational Burnout Among Nurses: Personal, Professional, and Environmental Determinants

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Background: Occupational burnout is a widespread problem in nursing, rooted in chronic stress and the demands of patient care, with consequences for staff wellbeing, organizations, and care quality.

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Aim: To assess the severity of burnout among nurses and identify sociodemographic and work-related correlates of risk; to examine associations between burnout, job satisfaction, life satisfaction, and dispositional optimism.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional study included 123 nurses/midwives employed in a hospital and outpatient clinic in Wrocław. Instruments: Maslach Burnout Inventory (22 items), Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS), Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS/SSP), and LOT-R for dispositional optimism. An extended sociodemographic and professional survey was collected. Statistical analyses followed the prespecified plan.

Results: The sample showed a moderate risk of burnout. Higher burnout co-occurred with lower job and life satisfaction and lower optimism (statistically significant trends). Risk factors included older age, longer tenure, living alone, childlessness, family problems, insufficient sleep and leisure time, shift work, higher patient load (especially adult wards), and lower income. Income differentiated results across JSS/SSP, SWLS, and Maslach scores (e.g., Maslach: 7.31 vs. 9.68; $p=0.016$). Supportive workplace relationships—particularly with supervisors—were protective.

Conclusions: (1) Nurses exhibit a moderate risk of burnout, most strongly linked to diminished satisfaction and optimism. (2) Both personal characteristics and work conditions (shift schedules, patient load, income) play important roles. (3) Multidimensional interventions are recommended: communication and anti-burnout training, stress-reduction and team-support programs, and organizational changes targeting workload and supervisor–staff relationships.

Key words: burnout, nurses, job satisfaction, life satisfaction.

**Quality of Life in Families of Children with Pulmonary Hypertension: A
Cross-Sectional Study**

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Background: Pediatric pulmonary hypertension (PH) burdens the functioning of the entire family. With therapeutic advances, assessing health-related quality of life (HRQoL) has become integral to comprehensive care.

Aim: To determine the level of HRQoL in families of children with PH and identify sociodemographic and clinical factors associated with poorer outcomes.

Material and methods: A cross-sectional study included 28 child–caregiver dyads. Children were 4–17 years old (mean 10), caregivers 29–57 (mean 43). Caregivers completed the SF-36 and an author-designed questionnaire; children and caregivers completed adjunct author tools. Normality was checked with the Shapiro–Wilk test. Variables covered family and economic context, cardiac surgery, and hospitalization frequency.

Results: Caregivers most often rated their HRQoL below population levels. Very high emotional burden was reported by over half of respondents, with anxiety and sadness predominating. Poorer HRQoL was associated with older child age, need for cardiac surgery,

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frequent hospitalizations, and limitations in the child's physical activity. The child's illness frequently forced withdrawal from employment (at least temporarily in most cases), while extensive grandparental support was uncommon. Although many families described their material situation as good, day-to-day functioning was strained by care coordination and indirect costs.

Conclusions: Pediatric PH substantially reduces family HRQoL, especially in emotional and social domains. Routine HRQoL monitoring should be embedded in pediatric PH care, alongside multidimensional interventions: psychological support for parents and siblings, organizational solutions that facilitate caregiving and continued employment, and targeted health education to mitigate disease burden.

Key words: pediatric pulmonary hypertension; quality of life; caregivers (parents) of children with PH.

**Primary Care Nurses in Coordinated Care and the Adult Health Check
(2022–2025): Tools, Roles, and Early Outcomes**

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Background: Since late 2022, Poland has been scaling up coordinated primary care and launched an adult health check programme (*Moje Zdrowie – Bilans Zdrowia Osoby Dorosłej*). Both reforms strengthen nurse-led, team-based prevention and chronic care while leveraging e-health tools (IKP/e-prescriptions/e-referrals/EDM).

Objective: To review the scope of coordinated care in Polish PHC, the structure of the Adult Health Check, and the comprehensive role of PHC nurses within European evidence on integrated care.

Methods: Narrative review of PubMed and grey literature (MoH/NFZ/CEZ legal and technical documents, OECD/WHO reports) from 2020–2025.

Conclusions: PHC nurses are pivotal to risk assessment, health education, coordination and continuity. Adult Health Check – anchored in IKP, standardized questionnaires and bundled labs – can systematize prevention, but success depends on interoperability, staffing and digital inclusion.

Key words: coordinated primary care; adult health check; PHC nurse; e-health.

**Legal liability in cases of wrongful conception and wrongful birth in the
Polish and American legal systems**

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This addresses the issue of civil liability of doctors for violating patients' rights to make informed decisions regarding abortion and family planning, with particular emphasis on claims for wrongful birth and wrongful conception. The analysis was conducted on a comparative legal basis, covering the Polish and American legal systems.

In the course of the research, three main categories of claims were identified. The first is wrongful conception, which refers to situations where medical negligence results in the unplanned conception of a child. The second is wrongful birth, which covers cases where a doctor's error (e.g. failure to detect a fetal defect) prevents a decision to terminate the pregnancy, resulting in the birth of a child with severe developmental defects. The last and most controversial category is wrongful life. It refers to claims by a child based on the mere fact of being born as a result of medical negligence.

An analysis of case law revealed significant differences between the legal systems analyses. In the United States, where reproductive rights are constitutionally protected, case law broadly allows claims for wrongful birth and wrongful conception, while generally rejecting the concept of wrongful life. In Poland, there are no specific regulations in this area, and the

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courts apply general provisions on civil liability. As the analysis of case law shows, Polish law only allows limited financial claims, while refusing compensation for the harm suffered.

In summary, despite the theoretical possibility of pursuing claims, the Polish legal system does not provide full legal protection to victims. In conclusion, directions for possible legislative changes were proposed that could contribute to better protection of the interests of aggrieved patients.

Key words: wrongful birth, wrongful conception, physician's civil liability, patient rights, informational duty

Factors Influencing Occupational Burnout Among Midwives

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Introduction: Burnout syndrome is an increasingly recognized phenomenon among midwives. Shift work, high professional responsibility, stress, and emotional burden associated with caring

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for patients during critical life moments increase the risk of reduced job satisfaction, lower quality of life, and depressive symptoms.

Aim: The aim of the study was to assess the level of occupational burnout among midwives and to determine its relationship with sociodemographic, psychological, and occupational factors.

Material and Methods: The study included 100 midwives employed in various healthcare facilities. A diagnostic survey method was applied using an author's questionnaire and standardized research tools: the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI), Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R), Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS), Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), and General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES). Statistical analysis was performed using comparative and correlation tests.

Results: The overall level of occupational burnout among the study group was moderate, with emotional exhaustion being the most dominant dimension. The participants presented a moderate level of optimism and life satisfaction, a low level of depressive symptoms, and an average level of self-efficacy. Significant associations were observed between lower burnout levels and a greater number of children, higher optimism, and stronger coping self-efficacy.

Conclusions: Occupational burnout among midwives poses a real threat to both the quality of patient care and the well-being of this professional group. Preventive strategies should include psychological support, strengthening resilience, and organizational interventions aimed at reducing stress and workload. Professional support programs may contribute to lowering the risk of burnout and improving the overall quality of life of midwives.

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Nursing Care of a Patient After Orthognathic Surgery

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Introduction: Gnathic deformities represent a significant health problem, leading to both functional and aesthetic impairments that may negatively affect patients' quality of life. Surgical treatment of skeletal craniofacial anomalies requires an interdisciplinary approach, with nursing care playing a crucial role in the perioperative period.

Aim of the Study: The aim of this study was to present the case of a patient undergoing orthognathic surgery and to highlight the role of comprehensive nursing care in the postoperative period, with particular emphasis on the identification of nursing problems, planning and implementation of interventions, and evaluation of their effectiveness.

Case Report: The case concerns a 25-year-old female patient with a gnathic deformity, qualified for BIMAX surgery with genioplasty. During hospitalization, corrective osteotomies of the maxilla and mandible were performed; however, genioplasty was abandoned due to intraoperative complications. In the postoperative period, the patient experienced multiple nursing problems, including facial swelling, breathing difficulties, impaired oral intake, pain,

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communication disorders, mood disturbances, nausea, as well as the occurrence of a pressure ulcer and urinary tract infection. Nursing interventions were aimed at symptom relief, improvement of patient comfort, prevention of complications, education, and support in self-care. Implemented measures contributed to a reduction in symptom severity and improvement in the patient's overall functioning.

Conclusions: Nursing care in the postoperative period after orthognathic surgery plays a pivotal role in minimizing complications, improving comfort, and supporting the patient's adaptation to a new health condition. Preoperative preparation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and the involvement of family members in the care process are of key importance. Professional nursing interventions contribute to shortening the recovery period and enhancing the quality of life of patients following surgical treatment of gnathic deformities.

Key words: orthognathic surgery, nursing care, postoperative complications, craniofacial deformities

Nursing Care of a Patient with Down Syndrome

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Introduction: Down syndrome is one of the most common chromosomal disorders, associated with a wide spectrum of somatic and cognitive abnormalities, including hypothyroidism, obesity, hepatic steatosis, sensory deficits, and obstructive sleep apnea. These comorbidities generate complex nursing challenges requiring holistic, individualized, and long-term management.

Aim: The objective of this study was to identify nursing problems in a patient with Down syndrome and to present the scope and outcomes of implemented nursing interventions in the home environment.

Material and Methods: The research employed a case study design using the nursing process. Data were collected from medical documentation, patient observation, and interviews with family caregivers. The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) was applied to assess pain severity.

Case Report: The case involved a 29-year-old male diagnosed with Down syndrome, complicated by obesity (body mass index 31.22), hypothyroidism, grade II/III hepatic steatosis, progressive bilateral cataract, history of penetrating keratoplasty of the right eye, hearing loss due to narrow auditory canals, psoriasis of the scalp, seborrheic dermatitis, onychomycosis, and lumbar spine pain secondary to flatfoot (VAS: 3). Nursing problems included dependence in daily activities, limited cognitive abilities, metabolic and endocrine disturbances, sleep-disordered breathing, and caregiver burden. Interventions focused on family education, dietary and physical activity modification, regular specialist consultations (ophthalmology, otolaryngology, pulmonology), positional training during sleep, recommendation of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP), psychosocial support, and use of orthopedic aids. Partial improvement in comfort was observed, though adherence to recommendations (dietary changes, CPAP use, visual aids) remained insufficient.

Conclusions: Comprehensive nursing care for adults with Down syndrome requires individualized, multidimensional interventions tailored to physical, cognitive, and social functioning. Interdisciplinary collaboration, continuous education, support for caregivers, and

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systematic monitoring of comorbidities are essential to improving patient outcomes and quality of life.

Key words: Down syndrome, nursing care, comorbidities, case study, caregiver support

The Impact of Shift Work on Sleep Quality Among Nurses

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Introduction: Sleep disorders are an increasingly common problem in the nursing profession. The issue tends to intensify, particularly among nurses engaged in shift work. The demanding and irregular schedules associated with nursing practice often disrupt circadian rhythms and impair recovery processes. This phenomenon has become a growing public health concern, as it not only affects the well-being of healthcare professionals but may also compromise patient safety. The main consequences of sleep disturbances include impaired concentration, elevated stress levels, depressive symptoms, and heightened anxiety. Sleep disorders can be classified

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as nocturnal insomnia, difficulties with sleep initiation during the night, excessive daytime sleepiness, as well as anxiety and disturbances in daytime functioning.

Aim of the Study: The primary aim of this study was to assess the impact of shift work on sleep disturbances among nurses.

Materials and Methods: The study was conducted using the diagnostic survey method. The study group consisted of 100 nurses (89% women and 11% men). Data collection was carried out between January 2024 and March 2024. Research material was obtained through anonymous questionnaires completed by participants using Google Forms. The survey included a self-designed sociodemographic questionnaire and two standardized instruments: the Insomnia Severity Index (ISI) and the Fatigue Assessment Scale (FAS).

Results: The majority of respondents were women. The findings revealed that shift work affects sleep disturbances, although no significant association was found with perceived fatigue. The study confirmed that the consumption of caffeine, energy drinks, and increased tobacco use escalates with the severity of sleep disorders. Furthermore, the influence of comorbidities on sleep disturbances was confirmed, as well as the impact of the number of working hours and multiple workplaces on sleep quality.

Key words: shift work, sleep disorders, nurses, insomnia, fatigue.

**Women's Knowledge, Beliefs, and Attitudes Regarding COVID-19
Vaccination in Pregnancy**

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Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on public health, with pregnant women identified as a group particularly vulnerable to complications. Despite recommendations from scientific societies, COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy continues to raise concerns and uncertainty among patients. Women's knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes toward vaccination play a crucial role in the decision-making process.

Aim: The aim of this study was to assess the level of knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes of women regarding COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy and to identify factors influencing the decision to be vaccinated.

Material and Methods: The study was conducted between April and May 2023 among 200 women who were pregnant during the pandemic years 2020–2023. A diagnostic survey method was employed using a self-designed questionnaire and the Fear of COVID-19 Scale (FCV-19S). Data were analyzed using Pearson's χ^2 test and the Mann–Whitney U test.

Results: The mean age of participants was 30.6 years. Most respondents had higher education (73%), with 16% representing a medical background. In total, 31% of women decided to be vaccinated against COVID-19 during pregnancy, while 47.5% refused vaccination. The main motivation for vaccination was fear of contracting COVID-19 (85.5%), whereas refusal was primarily justified by concerns about vaccine safety (84.2%). Vaccinated women demonstrated higher levels of knowledge and greater trust in the medical community. The overall level of fear of COVID-19 among respondents was low to moderate.

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Conclusions: The decision to receive COVID-19 vaccination during pregnancy remains a complex process influenced by knowledge, attitudes, and social environment. The findings highlight the necessity of intensifying educational activities by healthcare professionals and providing reliable health communication to increase vaccine acceptance among pregnant women.

Key words: COVID-19 vaccination, pregnancy, vaccine attitudes, health beliefs, maternal health

**Knowledge and Attitudes Toward First Aid Among the General
Population: A Cross-Sectional Study**

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Introduction: Immediate first aid can significantly improve survival and outcomes in emergencies, yet global studies show persistent deficits in public knowledge and readiness to act. Despite widespread awareness campaigns, fear of error, low confidence, and insufficient training remain major barriers. Assessing public knowledge, attitudes, and perceived competence is crucial to identify educational gaps and design effective training strategies.

Aim: To assess the level of knowledge and readiness to provide first aid among adults and to identify factors influencing these outcomes.

Material and Methods: An online cross-sectional survey was conducted via Google Forms among 202 adults aged 18–83 years (mean 42.4 ± 14.9), with 65.3% women and 79.2% employed respondents. Most participants (75.2%) represented non-medical professions; 65.3% had completed a first aid course. The questionnaire included socio-demographic items, attitude statements rated on a 5-point Likert scale, and a 10-question single-choice knowledge test (score 0–10; 0–3 = low, 4–6 = average, 7–10 = high). Data were analysed in MS Excel 365 and STATISTICA 13.3 using the Chi-square test at $p \leq 0.05$.

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Results: Most respondents (92.1%) declared they would always call for medical help, even if capable of performing resuscitation independently. Over half (56.4%) felt confident using an automated external defibrillator (AED), though only 48% knew its location nearby. Confidence was higher when assisting relatives (72.7%) than strangers (56.4%). Training strongly influenced knowledge level: among those who had completed first aid courses, 89.4% achieved high scores versus 65.7% without training. The main barriers to providing aid were fear of making a mistake and lack of practice opportunities.

Conclusions: Although attitudes toward first aid are generally positive, practical readiness and knowledge remain moderate, particularly among untrained individuals. Educational interventions should emphasize hands-on training, address psychological barriers, and promote early first aid education within non-medical populations.

Key words: First aid; Public awareness; Emergency response; Training effectiveness

**Shift Work, Dietary Habits, Lifestyle and Health Problems in Healthcare
Personnel: A Cross-Sectional Survey**

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Introduction: Shift work disrupts circadian rhythms, metabolism and hormonal balance. In healthcare, around-the-clock duties and limited recovery magnify effects on sleep, appetite and energy, fostering unhealthy eating and stress. These associations were analysed among healthcare professionals working shifts.

Aim: To assess the impact of shift work on dietary habits, lifestyle and health problems among healthcare personnel.

Material and Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 144 healthcare workers, including nurses, physicians and paramedics, of whom 53.5% worked shifts. An original, author-designed questionnaire was used to collect data on work schedules, dietary

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habits, lifestyle behaviours, and self-reported health complaints. The collected data were analysed in Microsoft Excel 365 and STATISTICA 13.3 software. The Chi-square test of independence was applied to assess the relationships between variables. In all analyses, the significance level was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: Compared with day workers, shift workers less often ate regular meals at work (40.3% vs 83.6%), more often ate at night (54.5% vs 11.9%), more frequently reported appetite changes (44.2% vs 9.0%), and had difficulty maintaining a healthy diet (59.7% vs 19.4%; all $p < 0.001$). Sports participation did not differ. Shift workers more often reported that work affected their physical-activity habits (70.1% vs 17.9%; $p < 0.001$) and had less time for rest (adequate rest: 49.4% vs 67.2%; $p = 0.031$). They also more often reported sleep problems (68.8% vs 17.9%), digestive problems (57.1% vs 17.9%), weight problems (49.4% vs 17.9%), cardiovascular problems (49.4% vs 11.9%), stress (58.4% vs 32.8%), and physician consultation (54.5% vs 4.5%; $p \leq 0.002$).

Conclusions: Among healthcare personnel, shift work is associated with irregular eating, altered activity patterns, reduced recovery time and higher prevalence of sleep, digestive, cardiovascular and weight-related problems as well as stress. Organizational policies should ensure protected recovery time, access to healthy meals round-the-clock, and support for sleep hygiene and stress management.

Key words: Shift work; Healthcare personnel; Dietary habits; Lifestyle

**Perception of Medical Care Quality Among Parents of Hospitalized
Children in Surgical and Non-Surgical Wards: A Comparative Study**

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Introduction: Parents' experiences during their child's hospitalization influence trust in healthcare and perception of care quality. Evaluating how families assess staff empathy,

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communication, and organization in pediatric wards helps identify strengths and areas for improvement in patient-centered care.

Aim: To assess and compare the perceived quality of care among families of children hospitalized in surgical and non-surgical pediatric wards at the University Hospital in Zielona Góra.

Material and Methods: The study was conducted between December 2024 and February 2025 among 120 parents (83.3% women; mean age 40.1 ± 8.6 years) of children aged 1–17 years. Half of the children were hospitalized in the surgical ward and half in the non-surgical ward. A diagnostic survey using a 26-item author-designed questionnaire was applied. Data were analyzed in MS Excel 365 and STATISTICA 13.3 using the Chi-square and Mann–Whitney U tests at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Results: The mean overall rating of care quality was 4.73 ± 0.44 (1–5 scale) and did not differ between wards ($p = 0.209$). Parents from surgical wards rated the admission process higher (4.72 vs 4.43; $p = 0.005$). Availability of staff was adequate for 97.5% of respondents, and competence for 95.8%. Emotional support for children was reported by 92.5% of parents, more often in surgical wards (96.7% vs 88.3%), particularly regarding empathy and anxiety reduction ($p \leq 0.01$). No differences were found in communication, information access, or parental engagement ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusions: Parents reported very high satisfaction with pediatric care in both wards. Organizational aspects and emotional support were rated slightly higher in surgical units. Regular assessment of family experiences can further improve communication and emotional support standards in pediatric care.

Key words: Pediatric care; Parental satisfaction; Hospitalized children; Quality of healthcare

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Factors influencing the perception of workload among Slovak nurses

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Introduction: Given its impact, the workload of nurses represents a huge health, economic, and social problem. Studies have long pointed to the fact that the nursing profession is associated with a high degree of difficulty and exposure to many stressors.

Objective: The aim of this paper is to highlight the subjectively perceived level of workload and analyze the factors that significantly influence it.

Sample and methods: Data was collected using an online questionnaire. The survey, which is a pilot study for the project Workload of Nurses 011KU- 4/2024, was conducted on a sample of 265 nurses, with respondents selected at random.

Results: In the sample we monitored, the median value in eight of the ten scaled items of Meister's questionnaire was equal to or higher than the critical median value for the given item. Nurses therefore subjectively perceived the workload as very intense in most of the parameters monitored. We identified the following factors as having the most intense impact on the subjectively perceived level of stress: 1. relationships in the workplace - reported by 69,2 % of the sample, 2. management by senior staff, reported by 62,1% of respondents, the nature of the work itself was identified as one of the factors that significantly influences the perception of workload by 24.1% of the sample, and patient behavior and demands by 16,9 %.

Conclusion: Perception of workload is determined by a combination of individual, organizational and systemic factors. Identification of these factors points to the need for systemic changes and targeted interventions at the level of work, organizational culture and mental health support for nurses.

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Key words: workload, nurses' workload, workload factors, working conditions, Meister questionnaire

**Comparison of the Burnout Syndrome Among Nursing Staff in Internal
Medicine Departments in Poland and Cyprus**

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Introduction: Occupational burnout is a phenomenon commonly observed among healthcare professionals, including nursing staff. The nature of this profession often involves both physical and emotional strain, which, over the long term, may lead to chronic fatigue associated with one's professional duties.

Objectives: The aim of this study is to determine and compare the level of occupational burnout among nursing staff working in internal medicine wards in hospitals in Poland and Cyprus, as well as to identify factors influencing the obtained results. Furthermore, the research seeks to propose potential solutions that could contribute to reducing the level of occupational burnout.

Method: The study involved a total of 52 respondents – 26 members of nursing staff employed in an internal medicine ward in a Cypriot hospital and 26 working in a corresponding

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department in Poland. The research was conducted using a questionnaire based on the Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (CBI), which consists of 19 questions.

Results: The level of occupational burnout among nurses working in internal medicine departments was higher in Poland, while in Cyprus it remained low (38.8%) and in Poland moderate (58.6%).

The main factors influencing the level of occupational burnout include long working hours, staffing shortages, and the interpersonal atmosphere among the staff.

Conclusion: The observed phenomenon of burnout among nurses impacts their quality of life and the quality of patient care. Support programs for nursing staff may be necessary, such as improved working conditions, psychological support, and stress management training.

Key words: nurses, occupational burnout

The Importance of Sleep in Child Development

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Sleep is essential for a child's proper development. We spend approximately one-third of our lives asleep. Through the secretion of growth hormone during sleep, children grow and develop their brain, influencing memory and concentration. Proper sleep supports emotional development, regulating mood and behavior. Adequate sleep quantity and quality also strengthens the immune system, making children less likely to suffer from infections. During sleep, a child's brain processes and consolidates new information, experiences, and memories. Sleep is fundamental for the development of speech, memory, concentration, and learning abilities. Sleep deprivation can lead to irritability and hyperactivity. Advances in development, especially technology, provide access to artificial light sources, such as lighting and electronic screens, which expose children to blue light that can disrupt sleep cycles.

Key words: child sleep, brain development, memory and concentration, emotional regulation, blue light

The Impact of Precocious Puberty on Children's Mental Health

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Precocious puberty is defined as the onset of pubertal symptoms before the age of 8 in girls and before the age of 9 in boys. Research indicates that precocious puberty is associated with the development of mental disorders, including substance abuse. Mental disorders related to puberty are observed up to nine times more frequently in girls than boys. The most common mental disorders include depression, anxiety disorders, oppositional defiant disorder, and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. Researchers emphasize that caregivers should be aware of the potential for mental disorders in children with precocious puberty.

Nursing care of a patient with autoimmune hepatitis

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Introduction: The subject of the work is the care of a patient with autoimmune hepatitis. This disease was described in 1950 by Jan Gösta Waldenström, is characterized by chronic

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inflammation of the liver and occurs mainly in women. In 1994, the name "autoimmune hepatitis" was officially adopted. This is an important topic because there is a lack of research in this area regarding the role of nurses in caring for patients with autoimmune hepatitis. This study was based on medical records, observation, interviews, and professional literature.

Aim of the study: The aim of this study is to present the biopsychosocial state of a patient suffering from autoimmune hepatitis and the responsibilities of a nurse caring for this patient. Furthermore, an important aspect of the study is to highlight the nursing challenges faced by this patient.

Material and Methods: The research method employed in this study was an individualized care process based on a case study. Various research techniques, including interviews, observations, and documentation analysis, were used to determine the patient's care model, her care issues, and health status. Furthermore, standardized scales and tests were used to develop the care process: the Body Mass Index (BMI), the Tinetti Test (short version), the Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA), the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), and the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS).

Results: Autoimmune hepatitis is a rare disease of unknown cause, more common in women. It is characterized by chronic liver inflammation and the presence of autoantibodies. Symptoms are nonspecific, making early diagnosis difficult. Treatment involves long-term immunosuppressive therapy (prednisone, azathioprine) and requires medical monitoring. In the described case, the treatment resulted in improvement and required psychological support and nutritional education. Effective care for patients with autoimmune hepatitis requires a holistic approach and a collaborative therapeutic team.

Conclusions: The patient's primary care challenges included weight loss with a risk of malnutrition, fatigue, jaundice, anxiety, and low mood. Care focused on symptom relief, emotional support, and education regarding nutrition and post-discharge treatment. Nursing support positively impacted the patient's well-being and motivation. The goals of care were achieved.

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Key words: autoimmune hepatitis, nursing care

Quality of life of patients after heart transplantation

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Introduction: The concept of quality of life is a complex one, which makes it the focus of many scientific fields such as psychology, sociology, philosophy, economics as well as medicine. Each of these fields analyses quality of life from its own theoretical and methodological perspective, leading to different definitions and research approaches. In medical terms, the concept of quality of life has gained particular importance in the context of assessing the health status of patients and the effectiveness of therapeutic treatments and interventions. A key role in standardising the approach to this issue was played by the World Health Organisation (WHO), which presented a definition of quality of life acceptable to the international scientific and medical community at the 1993 Copenhagen Conference. This

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definition takes into account both objective and subjective aspects of human functioning. It emphasises that quality of life cannot be assessed solely on the basis of biological or clinical parameters, but must also include individual experiences, perception of health, social relationships, level of independence, spiritual beliefs and the influence of the external environment. Nowadays, quality of life, especially in the health-related quality of life (HRQoL) perspective, has become an important research and diagnostic tool used, for example, in palliative medicine, geriatrics, oncology or rehabilitation. Measuring patients' quality of life makes it possible to assess the effectiveness of therapeutic interventions and to plan care tailored to the individual needs of patients.

Aim of the study: The aim of this study was to assess the quality of life and severity of depressive symptoms among heart transplant patients, and to identify factors that differentiate the level of depression and those related to subjective quality of life assessment. Sociodemographic variables, time since transplantation, and retrospective data on participants' mental state before surgery were included in the analysis.

Material and methods: The study was conducted in a group of 91 people. The criteria for entering the study were status after heart transplantation, age above 18 years and intellectual capacity to complete the questionnaires. To carry out the study, a diagnostic survey method was used with such research tools as the author's socio-demographic questionnaire, the Beck Depression Scale and the WHOQOL-BREF Quality of Life Assessment Questionnaire. The results were statistically analysed.

Results: The results showed that almost two-thirds of the participants were not experiencing symptoms of depression at the time of the study, while the remainder reported severity of depression at mild, moderate or severe levels. Quality of life was rated highest in the environmental and mental domains and lowest in the physical domain. The analysis showed significant correlations between depression severity and quality of life scores in all four WHOQOL-BREF dimensions, confirming the negative impact of depressive symptoms on transplant patients' functioning. In addition, depression levels were found to be significantly

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higher in younger patients and in women. In contrast, time since heart transplantation was not significantly associated with quality of life, suggesting that other factors - including psychological factors - play a more important role in this regard. The results also indicate a significant increase in the prevalence of depressive symptoms after surgery, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring of patients' mental state also during the recovery period.

Conclusions: The results of this study indicate that the quality of life of heart transplant patients is determined by both medical and socio-demographic factors. Time since surgery, absence of complications, higher education, living in a relationship and living in an urban area were associated with better functioning and higher subjective quality of life scores. A significant association was observed between the severity of depressive symptoms and reduced scores in individual quality of life domains. Those not experiencing depressive symptoms declared higher levels of life satisfaction and better physical and psychological well-being. Patients struggling with preoperative depression had a higher risk of symptom recurrence, but in many cases improvements in their health after transplantation had a positive impact on their mental wellbeing. These findings support the need for comprehensive patient care, including not only somatic treatment but also psychological support.

Key words: quality of life, quality of life assessment, heart transplantation, post-operative depression

Positive health behaviors and the level of physical activity of working women during pregnancy

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Aim of the study: The aim of the thesis was to multidimensionally assess the influence of selected sociodemographic factors on the level of positive health behaviour and physical activity in pregnant women who remain active.

Materials and methods: The study was conducted using a diagnostic survey method. Two standardised tools were used: the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ - short version) and the Questionnaire for the Assessment of Positive Health Behaviours (PHBS). 134 Pregnant, economically active women participated in the study.

Results: The results of the statistical analysis confirmed the existence of significant relationships between the level of physical activity and health behaviours and variables such as age ($\chi^2 = 19.86$; $p \leq 0.01$), marital status ($H=16.16$, $p \leq 0.001$), place of residence ($\chi^2 = 19.28$; $p \leq 0.05$), number of children ($H=12.16$, $p \leq 0.01$) and income level ($H=29.67$, $p \leq 0.001$). The following results were obtained from the IPAQ questionnaire: 80 women (59.70%), rated their activity, as sufficient, 31 women (23.13%) as high and 23 women (17.16%) as insufficient. A significant positive relationship was also identified between the overall level of positive health behaviour and physical activity ($H=14.77$, $p \leq 0.001$).

Conclusions:

- Marital status significantly differentiates the level of positive behaviours age of female respondents influences the level of physical activity.
- Place of residence differentiates physical activity levels.
- The number of children one has influences positive health behaviour.

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- Type of work, and form of work have no significant effect on physical activity levels of pregnant women.
- The level of net income is significant for both the level of positive health behaviour and physical activity.
- There is a positive relationship between the overall level of positive health behaviour and activity level.

Key words: positive health behaviours, physical activity, pregnant women,

The impact of ulcerative colitis on the professional and psychosocial life of patients

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Introduction: Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic inflammatory bowel disease that extends beyond the physical dimension. In addition to somatic symptoms such as abdominal pain and chronic fatigue, the disease significantly impacts patients' social functioning and family relationships. The embarrassment associated with frequent bowel movements often leads to social isolation, decreased mental well-being, and chronic stress.

Aim of the study: The aim of the study was to assess the impact of UC on the professional activity and daily life of patients, with particular emphasis on psychosocial and family aspects.

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Material and methods: The study was conducted among 41 patients aged 18-80 years, hospitalized or treated on an outpatient basis at the University Clinical Hospital in Wrocław. A proprietary questionnaire and standardized tools (SF-36v2, SWLS, WPAI:GH) were used to analyze sociodemographic data, professional activity, mental health, and social functioning.

Results: The disease significantly impacted professional activity, with average absenteeism rates of 16.08% and presenteeism rates of 33.66%. Over 40% of patients reported difficulty maintaining employment, and one in three considered changing jobs. Concurrently, UC limited participation in family and social life. Patients often reported fatigue, abdominal pain, and embarrassing discomfort associated with their symptoms, resulting in withdrawal from social relationships and family. Mean scores for social functioning (46.95%) and mental health (45%) were lower than those in the general population. Support from family and loved ones played a significant adaptive role, reducing the risk of isolation and stress.

Conclusions: UC not only reduces occupational productivity and generates economic costs but also disrupts patients' social and family functioning. The results highlight the importance of a holistic approach to treatment, including psychosocial interventions, strengthening family support, and community education, to improve patients' quality of life.

Key words: ulcerative colitis, quality of life, psychosocial impact, work productivity, family functioning.

Support for caregivers of children with cancer

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The incidence rate of cancer among children is approximately 145 new cases per year per 1 million children. This trend indicates that the demand for care and monitoring of health status in terms of later consequences of oncological disease will increase.

The aim of this work is to evaluate the support received by caregivers of children with cancer.

Methods: questionnaire survey. The following was used:

- self-authored survey questionnaire
- Scale of the Life Situation of Parents of Children with Oncological Diseases

Material: 50 questionnaires were obtained from mothers of children hospitalized due to acute lymphoblastic leukemia from June to September 2023 at the hematology and oncology department.

Results: Almost half of the mothers surveyed (46%) have two children. All mothers responded that they stayed with their children in hospital more often than the father. The vast majority of mothers surveyed are in formal relationships (n=42). The most common source of support for mothers is their immediate family, next in line are friends, medical staff and extended family. There were no significant correlations between the caregiver's emotional functioning and their age, place of residence, education, number of children, or presence of chronic diseases. The results regarding the source of income and the assessment of one's own health were significant.

Conclusions

1. The most frequently chosen source of support for the respondents was their closest family

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and friends,

2. Cancer brings many difficulties, but mothers say the greatest difficulty is "the need to stay in the hospital" and " complications after chemotherapy",
3. The results regarding the source of income and the assesmentof one's own health turned out to be significant in the relationship between life situation and emotional functioning.

Key words: paediatric oncology, support, mothers of hospitalised children.

**On the Road to Delivery: Predicting Out-of-Hospital Births in Emergency
Medical Care**

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Introduction: Unplanned childbirth outside the hospital setting is a highly unpredictable event that creates substantial challenges for Emergency Medical Services (EMS) teams. The problem is particularly pressing in Poland, where EMS crews are typically composed of paramedics or nurses rather than obstetricians, which restricts the scope of immediate obstetric care. Despite notable progress in perinatal medicine, deliveries occurring beyond hospital facilities remain linked with elevated maternal and neonatal risks. The present study sought to identify key predictors of pre-hospital delivery in cases attended by EMS.

Methodology: We conducted a retrospective analysis of 5097 EMS records of laboring women in Poland from August 2021 to January 2022, of which 2927 were included in the final study sample. Multivariate logistic regression models with multiple imputation for missing data were used to identify predictors of pre-hospital delivery and adverse neonatal condition (Apgar ≤ 7) in EMS-managed childbirths.

Results: Pre-hospital birth was strongly associated with second-stage labor (OR ≈ 5.35 ; $p < 0.0001$), ruptured membranes (OR ≈ 8.7 ; $p < 0.0001$), fewer previous pregnancies (OR = 0.86; $p = 0.018$), and showed a trend with higher maternal heart rate (OR = 1.015; $p = 0.083$).

Conclusion: Rupture of membranes, second-stage labor, and fewer previous pregnancies are significant predictors of pre-hospital birth in EMS-managed cases. Early identification of these factors may enhance prehospital perinatal care and improve maternal and neonatal prognosis.

Key words: Emergency Medical Services; Labor; Pre-hospital birth; Obstetric